

Middle East University
Faculty of Philosophy and Theology

BARRIERS TO SHARING THE GOSPEL WITH
MUSLIMS IN MALAKAL, SOUTH SUDAN

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Islamic Studies

by

Gak Ngaw Nyoat Doak

May 2020

THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Islamic Studies

Middle East University

Faculty of Philosophy and Theology

Title: BARRIERS TO SHARING THE GOSPEL WITH MUSLIMS
IN MALAKAL, SOUTH SUDAN

Researcher: Gak Ngaw Nyoat Doak

Advisor: Larry Lichtenwalter, PhD

Date Completed: May 2020

Problem

Jesus' Great Commission urged His disciples to share the good news of his kingdom with everyone, including Muslims. Muslim Evangelism seems to be the most challenging field of Christian witnessing, but it is not possible to wait for a suitable and comfortable time to evangelize Muslims. In fact, the real challenge is not that Muslims are not responding to the Gospel message, it is that many Christians are reluctant to share the Gospel with Muslims.

Method

After reviewing the literature related to the topic, the researcher did a survey using the self-administered questionnaire for the respondents from the different Adventist churches. This study used the quantitative approach to gather information from active members of the Seventh-day Adventist church in Malakal.

Results

Although the Seventh-day Adventist message has been in Malakal for over thirty years, members of the SDA Church have been mostly focusing their witnessing to people from Christian and animist backgrounds. The Muslim community has been neglected.

Conclusion

The researcher realized the need and the importance of training Adventist Church members in Malakal and other parts of South Sudan in the area of understanding the Muslim's heart, and witnessing to them. This could possibly motivate them to share the Gospel with Muslims wherever possible, since there is no law that restricts conversion of Muslims to Christianity in South Sudan.

This work is dedicated to my beloved wife

Nyanhail Peter Pal

BARRIERS TO SHARING THE GOSPEL WITH
MUSLIMS IN MALAKAL, SOUTH SUDAN

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Islamic Studies

by

Gak Ngaw Nyoat Doak

APPROVAL BY THE COMMITTEE:

Larry Lichtenwalter, PhD, Advisor

Nancy Jean Vyhmeister, EdD, Reader

Larry Lichtenwalter, PhD, Dean

Date Approved

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	x
Chapter	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Problem	1
The Status of Islam in Malakal	2
Statement of the Problem.....	3
Purpose of the Research.....	5
Specific Objectives	5
Significance of the Research.....	6
Scope of the Study	6
Delimitations of the Study	6
Assumptions.....	6
Biblical Conceptual Framework	7
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	9
<i>Encountering the World of Islam</i>	9
<i>Muslim Evangelism</i>	11
<i>My Neighbour's Faith</i>	14
Existential Challenge.....	14
Intellectual Challenge.....	14
Territorial/Demographic Challenge.....	15
Political Challenge.....	15
Theological Challenge.....	16
Missionary Challenge.....	16
<i>Faith Development in Context</i>	16
3. THE HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF MALAKAL.....	18
Islam in South Sudan	18
Christian Mission in South Sudan	20
Roman Catholic Mission in Malakal.....	21
Presbyterian Mission in Malakal.....	23
Seventh-day Adventist Mission in Malakal	23
4. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OR POTENTIAL FOR WITNESSING TO MUSLIMS IN MALAKAL.....	25
Challenges for Witnessing to Muslims in Malakal.....	25
Sharia.....	25

Attitudes and Prejudices of Muslims.....	26
Islam as Superior to Every Other Religion.....	27
Slow Growth Discouraging the Workers	28
Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament	31
Who Is Muhammad?.....	31
Corruption of the Holy Scriptures.....	34
Jesus	35
Jesus as Son of God.....	36
The Trinity.....	39
Jesus' Death, Crucifixion and Resurrection	40
Fear of Persecution	42
Disunity among the Gospel Experts in Muslim Ministry	42
Opportunities for Witnessing to Muslims in Malakal.....	42
Social Connections between Christians and Muslims in Malakal.....	42
Muslims and the Three Angels' Messages	43
The Gospel Commission	44
God's Example of Mission and Self-Sacrificing Service	45
Islam's Shortcomings toward Meeting Human Needs	47
Islam Is a Missionary Religion	48
Da'wah.....	49
Jihad	50
Mosque.....	50
5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	52
Research Design.....	52
Study Location and Population.....	52
Sample.....	53
Data Collection Methods and Instruments.....	53
Data Collection Procedure	54
Data Organization and Analysis	54
Editing	54
Coding	54
Tabulation.....	54
Data Analysis.....	55
Ethical Considerations	55
Protection from Harm.....	55
Informed Consent	55
Confidentiality	56
Right to Privacy	56
6. RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH	57
Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents	57
Major Strategies Used by the Adventist Church to Share the Gospel with Muslims.....	58
House-to-House Evangelism	59
Public Evangelism in Villages.....	59
Missionary Strategy.....	60
Development of Adventist Learning Institutions	60
Use of Extreme Media (TV, Radio, Newspapers).....	60

Use of Social Media	61
Use of the Testimonies	61
Reasons that Lead to Reluctance of Adventists to Vigorously Share the Gospel with Muslims.....	61
Islamic Sharia (Law) Factors.....	63
Christian Perspective	63
Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament	63
Disunity	63
Economic Factors	64
7. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	65
Summary	65
Motivational Factors and Strategies.....	66
Motivational Factors.....	66
Motivational Strategies.....	67
Conclusions.....	68
Recommendations.....	70
Recommended Approaches	70
Recommended Understandings	71
Recommendations for Further Research.....	72
BIBLIOGRAPHY	73
APPENDIX: SELF-ADMINISTERED QUESTIONNAIRE.....	76
CURRICULUM VITAE.....	80

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First of all thanks to my advisor, Dr. Larry Lichtenwalter (PhD), President and, Dean, Faculty of Philosophy at Middle East University.

Secondly, my heartfelt and sincere thanks to Dr. Nancy Jean Vyhmeister (EdD), a retired Professor of World Mission at Andrews University; who was more than a reader to me. She also helped me in correcting my English.

Special recognition of the tireless effort of Dr. Shawna Vyhmeister (PhD), Professor and Research Director at Middle East University, who came at the right time to rescue the project when I had almost given up. She helped me with guidance, formatting, and proofreading.

I very much appreciate the constant encouragement from Dr. Clement Joseph Arkangelo Mawa (DMin), President, South Sudan attached territory.

Thanks to the Greater Upper Nile Field Administration, under the leadership of Pastor Mark Igga Mona, for moral and financial support.

Thanks to my beloved wife and children for giving me the time due to them to complete this work during my studies at Middle East University and at home.

Special thanks to my son Khan Gak for helping me with typing my work.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Problem

The Great Commission Jesus gave to His disciples, to “go and make disciples of all nations” (Matt 28: 19), did not exclude the Muslims.¹ However, many Christians today feel that it is too risky to share the Gospel with Muslim friends. The consequences of sharing the Gospel with Muslims can be devastating, they think. Both, the evangelist and the receiver of the Christian faith may lose their lives. Although evangelizing Muslims seemingly is the hardest “field of Christian witness,”² Ray Roth nevertheless wrote the following in his dissertation:

Work for the Muslims cannot wait for the fair skies and calm seas. The king’s business requires haste (1Sam 21:8). In this world of sin we will have wars and revolutions (John 16: 33). Bonds and afflictions awaited Paul in every city (Acts 20:23), but he never allowed them to delay or deter him (Acts 21:13). He was always ready for services (Rom 1:15) or sacrifice (Phil 2:17). Once Paul received his marching orders; he pressed forward without hesitation, knowing that God would hold Himself responsible for all the consequences that flowed from his obedience. Paul realized that safety and security were no guarantee of success. On the other hand, he recognized that difficulty and danger do not necessary spell disaster. Missionary work for Muslims . . . must be carried on in fair weather or foul. The real tragedy does not lie in the closed countries that we cannot enter. Closed countries are God’s responsibility. We can safely leave them with Him until He chooses to re-open them as promised. Open countries are our responsibility, but we neglect them at our peril.³

¹Ray Roth, “Attitudes and Approaches to the Evangelization of Muslims in the Middle East,” Doctor of Ministry dissertation, Andrews University, 1983, 143, andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1220&context=dmin.

²John Gilchrist, *Sharing the Gospel with Muslims: A Handbook for Bible-Based Muslim Evangelism* (Nairobi, Kenya: Oasis International, 2003), 4.

³Roth, “Attitudes,” 143.

Jesus commanded us to share the message of salvation through Him “with everyone,” because “all the authority in heaven and earth has been given” to Him (Matt 28:18). He also promised that He would be with us “always, to the very end of the age” (Matt 28: 20).⁴ The questions are: What is the status of Islam in Malakal? What are the hindrances and the opportunities for sharing the Gospel with a Muslim friend in Malakal? Why are the Seventh-day Adventist Church members in Malakal reluctant to share the Gospel with their Muslim neighbors and friends? How can the Seventh-day Adventist Church members in Malakal be motivated to share the Gospel with Muslims?

The Status of Islam in Malakal

Islam entered Malakal, as elsewhere in South Sudan, through slave traders, colonial Muslim soldiers, Islamic political agencies, and intermarriage. Because of these reasons, as well as others, the majority of the South Sudanese see Islam as the religion of the oppressors and those who have joined Islam are considered to be cultural betrayers.⁵

Generally, becoming a Muslim is very simple, because what is required is to profess the Islamic Shahada ‘declaration’ of “*La ilaha illa Allah Muhammadun Rasulu Allah*,” which is interpreted: “I bear the witness that there is no god but Allah, and Muhammad is the Messenger of Allah.’ . . . If you say these words, accepting them with your mind, believing them with your heart, and confessing them with your

⁴Greg Livingstone, *Planting Churches in Muslim Cities: A Team Approach*, (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Books, 2001), 25.

⁵Jack A. Abubakar Deng, “Vers Enteries: Islam in South Sudan” [مقالات: الإسلام] [في جنوب السودان] accessed August 6, 2007, www.sudaress.com/sudansite/649.

tongue, you become a Muslim and a member of the *umma*.”⁶ And once you become a Muslim, you are supposed to remain within Islam as long as you live on this earth. However, conversion from Islam to Christianity in Malakal is not highly restricted, even before the secession of Southern Sudan from the Northern part of Sudan in 2011. Muslims and Christians in Malakal are socially connected; they live together, as brothers and sisters. Like Christians, who go to their churches for prayer, Muslims also go to mosques for prayer as well. Nevertheless, Christians are still reluctant to share the Gospel with their Muslim brothers and sisters.

In the past, using the traditional method of reaching out to Muslims, the Christian work among the followers of Islam did not bear much fruit. This helps many to think that winning Muslims is an unachievable goal,⁷ ignoring that our duty is to bear witness, to plant the seed, while the growth is not ours. As Paul, sharing his experience working among the Gentiles with his colleague Apollo, said, “what after all, is Apollo? And what is Paul? . . . Only servants, through whom you came to believe, I plant and Apollo watered but, God made it grow” (1Cor 3: 5, 6). Is it possible to plant the seed of the Gospel among the followers of Islam? What are the hindrances and the opportunities for sharing the gospel with a Muslim friend in Malakal?

Statement of the Problem

In Malakal, as elsewhere, Christians are reluctant to share the word of God with Muslim neighbors or friends. This could sometimes be out of personal prejudices,

⁶Oland E. Mille, *Muslim Friends: Their Faith and Feeling; An Introduction to Islam* (St. Louis, MO: Concordia, 1995), 211.

⁷John Azumah, “Christian Witness to Muslims: Rationale, Approaches and Strategies,” *Missionalia* 34 (April 2006): 5.

coupled with lack of training in the area of Muslim evangelism. Fear of persecution and disunity among the Gospel workers are other reasons,⁸ despite the fact that the SDA Church has been in South Sudan for more than 40 years⁹ and in Malakal since 1985.¹⁰

However, members of the SDA Church have largely focused on witnessing to people from Christian and animist backgrounds. The Muslim community has not been prioritized, due to the previously mentioned reasons. Although the members of the SDA Church have tried to witness to people with Christian and animist backgrounds, to do this, they have mainly used traditional methods to spread the gospel. Various studies have shown, with sufficient evidence, that “with few exceptions, early Adventists in Muslim lands largely focused on sharing/witnessing their beliefs with other Christians, whether they were foreign groups or indigenous communities residing in lands occupied by Muslims.”¹¹ This method, as can now be seen, has not yielded tangible results among the Muslim communities in Malakal.

Currently the Adventist Church is making efforts to educate pastors in Islamic Studies through Adventist institutions of higher learning, to learn more about Islamic beliefs, as this will help to evangelize Muslim communities. However, the church is yet to have the first graduates in South Sudan, including Malakal. Without a proper

⁸Abner P. Dizon, “Issues in Adventist Muslim Ministry,” *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 8, no. 2 (2012): 5, 6.

⁹Roland Werner, William Anderson, and Andrew Wheeler, *Day of Devastation, Day of Contentment: The History of the Sudanese Church across 2000 Years* (Nairobi, Kenya: Paulines Publications Africa, 2010), 364.

¹⁰Gerald D. Karst, “Light Breaks Over Sudan,” *Mission: A Quarterly Report of World Mission*, April-June 1987, 21, 22.

¹¹Rick McEdward, “A Brief Overview of Adventist Witness among Muslims,” in Bruce L. Bauer, ed., *A Man of Passionate Reflection* (Berrien Springs MI: Department of World Mission, Andrews University, 2011), 248, 249.

strategy for witnessing among the Muslim community in the country, it will be difficult to accomplish the Great Commission in the vast population of South Sudan. The purpose of this thesis is to lay the basis for a strategy that is context-dependent to address the problem of evangelism of Muslims in Malakal.

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this research is to identify the key reasons that lead to reluctance of Adventist members to not vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends. This will lead them to catch a vision that would motivate them to witness to their Muslim neighbors and friends, especially in Malakal. Since Muslims are evidently in God's plan of salvation, like any other people, it is important to help the Church members to understand the necessity of reaching out to Muslims. Here lies the secret of the success of the Christian Mission. If the root takes fire, it is possible to burn the whole tree.

Witnessing to Muslims is a biblical mandate; it is our duty; it is an obligation; it is a must, it is not an option. Many think it costs too much, is an impossible mission, a waste of time, and not fruitful. We are only tools in God's hands; God gives fruit to his vineyard at the due time. We can only accept to work together with Him. If we give up our fear of rejection; our prejudices, and allow the Holy Spirit to change, and use us, the gospel will be preached to the entire nation of South Sudan.

Specific Objectives

1. To investigate major strategies used by Adventist Church members to share the Gospel with Muslim neighbors or friends.
2. To identify the key reasons that lead to reluctance of Adventist members to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends.

3. To establish motivational strategies to enable the Adventist Church to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends in Malakal.

Significance of the Research

The significance of this paper is to discover the best strategy for outreach and ways to motivate the Seventh-day Adventists members in Malakal to share the Gospel with Muslim neighbors or friends. The information that will come from this study will further contribute to the knowledge in the area of witnessing to Muslim communities for the Seventh-day Adventists Church. This will also help the Church to develop training programs to help church members in evangelism take the Word of God to all the people in South Sudan, without fear of rejection or prejudice.

Scope of the Study

The study was carried out in the town of Malakal, located in northeastern South Sudan. Muslims and Christians of different denominations, including Adventists, occupy the area. The study investigated motivating Seventh-day Adventist church members in Malakal to share the Gospel with Muslim friends.

Delimitations of the Study

This research study involved Seventh-day Adventist Church members living and congregating in Adventist churches in Malakal. The study was conducted to investigate the reasons why church members are reluctant to share the Gospel with the Muslim community in Malakal, in the Central Upper Nile State, in South Sudan.

Assumptions

It is assumed that Seventh-day Adventist members understood the purpose of this study and participated by providing cogent information to be used to develop a

mission strategy. This information was relevant to the context of South Sudan, in order to witness to the Muslim community in Malakal.

The study used a checklist interview. It was assumed that the checklist would capture useful information about the views of Seventh-day Adventist members regarding their reluctance, as well as the hindrances and opportunities that exist in Malakal to spread the Gospel to the Muslim community.

Biblical Conceptual Framework

This study is conceptualized on the biblical evidence and is based on the commission Jesus Christ gave all His followers (Matt 28:19): “Therefore go and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Spirit.” In this verse, “go” implies a serious warfare of spreading the gospel, as Jesus Christ is interested in a gospel army that is aggressive to win more people to Him using the Gospel in Malakal. The study focused on the members of the Seventh-day Adventist Church as the disciples with the marching orders to go forth and preach this Good News. Anchoring this study on Matthew 28:19 enabled the researcher to understand that these verses not only command the followers of Christ to go out into the field, but also to win more people to God’s kingdom, including Muslims, Christians, and non-believers. The people to be brought to Jesus are not only those with Christian faith, but everyone in the world, because Jesus came to save the entire world. Hence, the Gospel Commission is meant for all people. Persons baptized in the “name of the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit” will share the message as a sign that they have accepted Jesus as their personal Saviour.

Since the study was conducted among Seventh-day Adventist church members, the conceptual framework enabled the researcher to understand what makes them reluctant, the hindrances they face, and the opportunities that exist for the

members of our faith to take the Gospel to the entire population of Malakal. In essence, the conceptual framework of this study was more relevant because Jesus Christ has paved the way for us to preach the Gospel to all people and, as his followers, we can embrace this approach to bring more people to his kingdom. The conceptual framework will help in understanding how to witness to an individual or friend, members of the household, or neighbours in Malakal. The process of witnessing involves using different strategies that fit the context of the targeted population.

This biblical conceptual framework was also relevant in the methodological section, as it guided the researcher in developing tools relevant to the study. In essence, this helped the research to collect useful information and meet the objectives of the study.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section contains a review of the literature available on the topic of this study. Its purpose was to review the literature to understand how, in different settings, Christians have witnessed to Muslim communities, as well as the challenges and opportunities they encountered during their mission. Many books have been written on this topic, but the following four books will be included in the literature review: *Encountering the World of Islam*, *Muslim Evangelism*, *My Neighbor's Faith*, and *Faith Development in Context*.

Encountering the World of Islam

Keith E. Swartley edited *Encountering the World of Islam*.¹ This is one of the best training tools I have read in the area of witnessing to Muslims. Eighty authors who have lived in the Muslim world wrote it. Among the authors are experienced missionaries and scholars of Islam. The book is divided into twelve major parts, identified as “lessons.” The first three lessons (1–3) are about the development of Islam. Lessons 4–6 give insights about the expression of Islam. The following three Lessons (7–9) discuss Christianity in relation to Islam. The final three (10–12) give a Christian response to Islam.² This review will consider only Lessons 7 and 8.

¹Keith E. Swartley, ed., *Encountering the World of Islam* (Waynesboro, GA: Authentic Media, 2005), 1-15.

²Ibid., 1-15.

Lesson 7 discusses the cultural barriers of Christian witnessing to Muslims. The editor, as usual throughout the book, introduces it. He notes that the obstacles to Christian witnessing to Muslims are not based on theological barriers, but on sociological and cultural hindrances. When Muslims want to decide to follow Jesus, they are mostly faced with the following questions: What will be the reaction of my family? What are the consequences of my choice, to my customs, to my political and economic life, or my community, and my associates? Will this affect my loyalty to my household and my society? Is there anyone who will still be a friend to me? Who will marry me?³

Swartley has clearly pointed out that

Understanding cultural, sociological, historical, political, and economic concerns are of primary importance in our approach to Muslims. . . . But, if we fail to address sociological issues in our relationships with Muslims, they may reject our words and actions before ever really hearing or seeing the beauty of the gospel. . . . Muslims react strongly against so-called Christian behaviors: immodest dress, offensive diets, drunkenness, drug use, dysfunctional families, abortion, homosexuality, and other immorality demonstrated in television, movies, and pornography exported to Muslim communities.⁴

In Lesson 8, the following theological issues are discussed: Jesus Christ, his divinity, his title, Son of God, and his prophethood; Christ's crucifixion and resurrection; original sin, the oneness of God, and the question of the Christian concept of the Trinity. Also noted are the issues of the charges of the corruption of the Holy Scriptures, heaven or Paradise, and Hell. In the introduction to this lesson, the writer states that numerous Muslims have had "mistaken assumptions about Christian faith."⁵ Several are from Islamic doctrine, but others are from popular Muslim street

³Ibid., 227.

⁴Ibid., 228.

⁵ Ibid., 269.

inventions. The writer also wrote that, in a Christian response to those objections, we do not need to argue immediately to convince our Muslim friends that we are right theologically, but must try to win their confidence and put the Bible into their hands, praying that step by step the power of the Word of God will change these Muslim friends. Concerning the Christian concept of the Trinity, the writer also argued that the Trinity is even difficult for Christians to understand. Instead of a “vain argument”⁶ on this issue, it is better to assure our Muslim friends of our belief in the Oneness of God and continue to pray for God to help them “discern this concept.”⁷ The writer further explained the importance of “Christ’s death on the Cross, his payment for our sins by his blood and righteousness, and power over death, sin, shame, and fear that is a viable only through resurrection.”⁸ But he suggested that these issues should be introduced to the Muslims later, after they became familiar to the “rest of God’s revelation.”⁹

Muslim Evangelism

Philip Parshall, in his book *Muslim Evangelism*,¹⁰ described the gap that exists between the two largest world religions—Islam and Christianity—using the illustration of the difficulty in constructing bridges, which start with the careful survey of a suitable site, knowing the depth of the river, measuring the swiftness of the current, and checking the levels of the water. In addition, there is the issue of

⁶ Ibid., 269.

⁷ Ibid., 269.

⁸ Ibid., 269.

⁹ Ibid., 269.

¹⁰ Philip Parshall, *Muslim Evangelism: Contemporary Approaches to Contextualization* (Grand Rapids MI: Gabriel Publishing, 2003).

getting the right materials, and calculating the cost. If not handled well, the outcome will be a complete tragedy. God is the role model, who took the initiative in bridging the gulf between heaven and earth, by sending Jesus Christ into the world in human form. The following are the theological bridges to be used to introduce the Gospel to Muslims, as suggested by Philip Parshall: Quran the Muslims' Holy Book, The Old Testament Prophets, Jesus in the Quran, Sacrifice Festivals, Sufism, and Supernatural Experiences.¹¹

Parshall recommended the “use of the Quranic passages that point to a high view of the Scripture” at the early stages, when sharing the Gospel with Muslims. The Bible should be treated with high respect, the same way Muslims do to the Quran. Muslims are taught not touch a Quran with unpurified hands. “The average Muslim wraps his Quran in an expensive cloth and places it in a position of honor. It is very difficult for the Muslim to understand the casual manner in which a Christian may place his Bible on the floor or mark it up with pen or pencil. This amounts to the desecration of that which is sacred.”¹²

Secondly, Parshall considered the prophets of Old Testament times as the communal point between the Quran and the Old Testament. These “should be thoroughly explored. This may eventuate in a Muslim’s giving serious consideration to the Message that leads on from prophecy to prophetic fulfillment.”¹³ Islam considers prophets as special messengers of God. The most well known prophets to Muslims are: Adam, Noah, Ishmael, Moses, Jesus, and Muhammad. In Islamic

¹¹Ibid., 143, 144.

¹² Ibid., 145, 146.

¹³ Ibid., 150, 151.

teaching all prophets are considered human and not divine. Prophets are simply regarded as participants of God's revelation conveyed to them by angels.¹⁴

Thirdly, Parshall quoted Don McCurry, who notes that many Muslims came to Christ because they read about him in the Quran first. There should be no fear in "using the Quran as the beginning point for introducing the subject of Jesus." He further argued that Paul the apostle did the same by using the Greek literature in his Mars Hill sermon. Quranic teaching about Jesus could be used as an effective tool for reaching Muslims, since the Quran speaks about him positively and respectfully, without any criticism. The Quranic account of Jesus' birth is similar to the biblical account. The Quran's description "of Jesus as the Word of God helps us bridge the gap that exists between the Muslim and Christian understanding of Jesus's person and His relation to God. Certainly, this title is more helpful than others such as 'Son of God' or 'Lamp of God.'" ¹⁵

Fourth, Parshall suggests the Islamic Id Al Adha or Feast of Sacrifice as a potential bridge to connect Christianity with Islam. Muslims celebrate the Feast of Id to remember Abraham's willingness to sacrifice his own beloved Son Ishmael, but not Isaac, as taught by Jews and Christians. Every year at the time of Id Al-Adha, every Muslims family must slay an animal or share one with another family, or at least slay a chicken if they cannot afford a larger animal. "The animal must be without blemish and young." According to Parshall, "an average Muslim links the sacrifice to the sin offering as the Jew did in the old Testaments Times." ¹⁶

¹⁴ Ibid., 150, 151.

¹⁵ Ibid., 152, 155.

¹⁶ Ibid., 159, 160.

My Neighbour's Faith

In his book, *My Neighbour's Faith*, Dr. John Azumah discusses the existence of Islam in Africa, not as the religion of strangers, but as the religion of the neighbor and close relative.¹⁷ For the sake of this research, I will focus on Chapter 2, “Challenges Posed by Islam.”

In Chapter 2 Azumah portrays the challenges displayed by Islam toward Christianity. These are not only missionary challenges, since Islam is the only religion which is a missionary rival to Christianity; they are existential, intellectual, territorial, political, theological, and missiological.

Existential Challenge

Islam exists especially in Africa, not as a foreign religion or the religion of foreigners, but as an indigenous religion. It is the religion of the head of state, the neighbor, and the close relative.

Intellectual Challenge

Many post-colonial African leaders think that African heritage, whether material, cultural, or human, has been undermined in contact with the Christian West and that this was done through missionary activities, slave trade, and colonialism. For that reason, some of the African leaders have argued that Christianity should be rejected, while others suggested that it should only be adapted to the African culture.

¹⁷ John Azumah *My Neighbour's Faith: Islam Explained for Christians* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2008), https://www.amazon.com/My-Neighbours-Faith-Explained-Christians-ebook/dp/B07NHPZQVV/ref=sr_1_1?dchild=1&keywords=my+neighbour%27s+faith+azumah&qid=1587145381&sr=8-1.

On the other hand, they see Islam as “an African religion, or that it is more in tune with the African personality heritage than its Western-Christian rival.”¹⁸

Territorial/Demographic Challenge

Azumah clearly states that Islam, using Jihad between the seventh century and the seventeenth century,

displaced Christianity from what used to be Christian heartlands in the Middle East, North Africa, and Central and Eastern Europe, transforming Christian civilizations, into Islamic ones in Turkey, the Middle East and North Africa. The capital of present-day Turkey, Istanbul, used to be Constantinople, the city of Constantine, the first Roman Emperor to convert to Christianity in the fourth century. The Christian kingdoms of Armenia, Byzantium, Bulgaria, Serbia, Bosnia, Herzegovina, Croatia, Albania and parts of Poland and Hungary were conquered. In many of these places, churches were turned into mosques. What is today known as the Umayyad Mosque in Damascus, Syria, used to be the Cathedral of St John the Baptist, and his tomb is still located there.¹⁹

Political Challenge

Azumah further notes that Islam poses political challenges to Christianity, because Christians considered religion as an individual matter of choice, yet the church’s past involvement in the use of worldly power was a grave deviation from Christian norms. Muslims, nevertheless, look at any effort of transferring religion to the private scope as a “violation of Islam.” And according to the Muslims, Islam is a total way of life “and there can be no separation between private and public, spiritual and temporal, religion and politics, or church and state. They therefore make every effort to lay claim to the public space from which Christians tend to retreat.”²⁰ This means that while very few Christians may use their leadership position to advance the

¹⁸ Azumah, chap. 1, “Definition of the Problem.”15.

¹⁹ Azumah, chap. 2, “Territorial/Demographic Challenge.”, 24.

²⁰ Azumah, chap.2, “Political Challenge.”, 25.

cause of their religion without fear, “Very few Muslims would hesitate to do so. Muslims believe that the whole world belongs to God and that, as the only true believers, they have the right to rule the public space on his behalf.”²¹

Theological Challenge

Besides others challenges, Islam has posed a doctrinal challenge to Christianity. At the very start of his mission, Muhammad, the founder of Islam, saw himself equal with past prophets of the Judeo-Christian tradition and the Quran as an Arabic version of the Jewish-Christian Bible. But later Islam considered itself as the substitute for Christianity and Judaism.

Missionary Challenge

According to Muslim understanding, “Islam is a missionary religion, and the only religion that poses serious missionary challenges to Christianity.”²²

Faith Development in Context

In Chapter 7 of the book *Faith Development in Context*, Oscar Osindo discusses the ways Christians, especially Seventh-day Adventists, should “positively relate to the person of Mohammad and Islam in general.”²³ Osindo clearly states that “the people of the Book (Jews and Christians) confronted Mohammad theologically. However, by doing so, they alienated themselves from Muslim community. From the missiological point of view, they lost the opportunity to carry out the Great

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid., chap. 2, “Missionary Challenge.”, 27, 28.

²³ Oscar Osindo, “Relating to Mohammad and the Mosque,” in *Faith Development in Context: Presenting Christ in Creative Ways*, ed. Bruce Bauer (Berrien Springs, MI: Andrews University Press, 2005), 89.

Commission of Jesus.” He further reasoned that we might not be fair if we compared “Mohammad with the perfect ideal in the New Testament—Jesus Christ.”²⁴ We might do well to compare Mohammad with the rest of the canonical prophets, particularly the Old Testament prophets. Osindo also pointed out that it might “help us to relate mission logically to Mohammad and Quran.”²⁵

Dr. Osindo went further, saying that “perhaps if Mohammad had lived during the time of Joshua or David, he would be more accepted as a true Prophet.”²⁶

²⁴ Ibid., 192.

²⁵ Ibid., 193.

²⁶ Ibid., 202.

CHAPTER 3

THE HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF MALAKAL

Malakal is the second major city in South Sudan, after Juba, the capital. It lies in the northeast of the country; where the White Nile and Sobat rivers meet. It is currently the capital of the newly created Central Upper Nile State.¹

Islam in South Sudan

Although the Islamization of Sudan started in the eighth century in the North, the resistance of the Southern Sudanese animist tribes to Islam, coupled with the “geographic barriers that protected the southerners from Islam’s advance enabled them to retain their social and cultural heritage and their political and religious institutions. During the nineteenth century, the slave trade brought southerners into closer contact with Sudanese Arabs and resulted in a deep hatred for the northerners.”²

Nevertheless, Muslims did not give up their ambition, as a majority of Sudanese Muslims viewed the Islamization of southern Sudan as the Islamic gateway to Africa. Sir Sadig al-Mahdi, the grandson of the Sudanese Mahdi and a former Prime Minister in Sudan, once unveiled the agenda: “the failure of Islam in southern

¹Wikipedia contributors, "Malakal," *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Malakal&oldid=949300635>.

² Mohamad Hassan Fadlalla, *Short History of Sudan* (New York: iUniverse, 2004), 25.

Sudan would be the failure of Sudanese Muslims to international Islamic cause. Islam has a holy mission in Africa and southern Sudan is the beginning of that mission.”³

Islam in Malakal, the capital city of the current Central Upper Nile State, has Christianity as its rival missionary religion. Christianity first entered the former Upper Nile Province (currently Central Upper Nile State) through Kodok, an administrative capital established during Anglo-Egyptian government in the year 1899. The first Muslim missionaries who came to Kodok were Sufi Muslims, who arrived in four stages. The first initiative was by the South Sudanese Muslim Turks and Mahdiest captives from the Upper Nile Region, who came back from Omdurman when freed by the British after the year 1899. The movement was reestablished by the return of the White Flag southern Sudanese, led by Ali Abdel Latif Chol to the Upper Nile in 1924. The third group were individuals from police, prison services, and *Reyi al masri* (Egyptian irrigation) workers, who were South Sudanese Muslims who came to Malakal. The fourth group was of northern Muslims, who were government officials, soldiers, and western Sudan traders, mainly from Felleta. These introduced Buruhaiyya and Dousugiyya Sufi tariqas.⁴

In regard to religion in South Sudan, the South Sudan Embassy in Geneva, Switzerland, reports the following:

With regards to religious beliefs and practices, South Sudanese are mostly pluralistic, with a majority of them, about 85%, adhering to indigenous belief systems, which involve totems, lower gods and high God, and belief in the power of ancestors to look over the living. Others believe in both the indigenous systems and Christianity. There is also a very small percentage of Muslims. Traditionally, religion was never a source of conflict, as it was always inseparable from ethnic identity. In the indigenous religions, one is born into it, as one’s religion is the same as one’s blood, and therefore no

³ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 14.

⁴ Abdalla kerri Wani, *Islam in Southern Sudan: Its impact: Past, Present, and Future* (Khartoum, Sudan: Khartoum University Press, 2008).

room for efforts to convert others. But when the so-called religions of the book, Christianity and Islam ascended, the concept of proselytization and efforts to convert people became a question of placing the faiths in hierarchy, with local religions thought by foreign missionaries as inferior and the people needing their souls to be saved. This has long pitted the people against one another, resulting, at least partly, in protracted wars between the religion of the state in the old Sudan, Islam, and believers in other faiths in South Sudan who did not want to be forced into Islam. Otherwise, within South Sudan, religion is not just a question of coming to terms with the cosmos, but as much a way of life as it is a way of reckoning with the unknown, including the mystery of life and death.⁵

Christian Mission in South Sudan

The majority of historians and theologians who have written about the history of Sudanese Christianity agreed that the coming of the Christian missionaries to southern Sudan in the nineteenth century was not the beginning of Christian work in Sudan. Sudan was the home of Christianity from the conversion of the Nubian kingdom to Christianity in 540 AD until the early sixteenth century, when the Christian faith was almost completely “eradicated and replaced with Islam”⁶ in Sudan. Meanwhile, the coming of Christian missionaries to Sudan in the nineteenth century marked the beginning of modern Sudanese Christianity, which was not able to take root in northern Sudan, but was pushed to the southern part of the country. Furthermore, the first Christian missionaries who came to Southern Sudan were Roman Catholic, followed by American United Presbyterian missionaries, who came around 1900.

It is also important to briefly mention historical facts concerning the development of the Christian mission in South Sudan, focusing mostly on Catholic,

⁵ South Sudan Embassy and Mission in Geneva, “South Sudan: Religion,” southsudanmission.ch/southsudan-religion-29.

⁶ Francis M. Deng, “Sudan–Civil War and Genocide: Disappearing Christianity,” *Middle East Quarterly* 8 (2001): 13-21. '

Presbyterian, and Seventh-day Adventist mission in Malakal, currently the capital city of the Central Upper Nile State in the Republic of South Sudan.

Roman Catholic Mission in Malakal

The first Catholic attempt to evangelize Southern Sudan was initiated by Mgr. Knob Lehar and his team members, who left Khartoum on November 13, 1849, to visit Southern Sudan villages. In addition to “considerable sacrifice of the missionaries’ lives, especially from tropical disease, chiefly malaria,”⁷ there were other challenges, for example: “poor transport, vast distance, lack of resources, the variety of languages, cultural factors,”⁸ and the resistance of the local people. These and other issues made the efforts not bear much fruit.

Saint Daniel Comboni, who totally dedicated his life to evangelizing Africa, initiated the second trial. His motto was “Africa or death.” Comboni’s “most important contribution to the mission was his “plan for the regeneration of Africa by Africa.”⁹ For the implementation of his plan, Comboni suggested the following practical steps:

1. To establish mission institutions for religious and secular education in the cities of Eastern and Western Africa.
2. To train indigenous African boys and girls to serve in those places, contrary to Roman Catholic practice in those days.

⁷ Elia Toniolia, “The Centenary of the Roman Catholic Mission to Central Africa,” *Sudan Notes and Records* 27(1946): 120.

⁸ Anders Breidlid, ed., *A Concise History of South Sudan*, new ed. (Kampala, Uganda: Foundation Publishers, 2014), 108, 109, 146, 147.

⁹ Thomas P. Kedini, “Suffering Churches in Sudan,” *Anglican and Episcopal History* 71 (2002), 156.

3. To train the foreign missionaries who came to Africa for better service.

Comboni was appointed as the Pro-vicar of the Vicariate for Central Africa, with headquarters in Khartoum, in May 1872. With the coming of Comboni, mission stations were opened in Al Obied, in the western Sudan, and Dilling in the Nubian mountains. Unfortunately, the death of Comboni, on October 10, 1881, in Khartoum, and the Mahdist revolution, which started the same year, led to the withdrawal of Catholic mission from Sudan. However, his initiative laid the foundation for current Roman Catholic mission in Sudan. Many Catholic schools and colleges bear the name of Comboni in Sudan today.¹⁰

The third Roman Catholic mission initiative in Southern Sudan was taken by the Verona fathers, who came to Sudan on January 4, 1900. However, the Verona fathers were not allowed to reopen missionary work in northern Sudan but instead they turned their emphasis to the South. Roman Catholic missionaries were the first to start Christian mission work in Malakal. Their mission was established for the first time at Lul, a town approximately twenty kilometers up-river from Fashoda (Kodok today). Father Ohrwalder, of the Verona fathers, was the first Catholic priest put in charge of the Lul mission station, established on February 11, 1901.¹¹ On January 10, 1933, it became “Mission Suiluris” of Kodak, under the Apostolic Vicariate of Khartoum. Five years later, on August 4, 1938, it grew into the Apostolic Prefecture of Kodok. The head office was moved to Malakal, the current capital city of what is today the Central Upper Nile State of the Republic of South Sudan. On July 14, 1949,

¹⁰ Werner, Anderson, and Wheeler, *Day of Devastation*, 126-147.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 168, 169.

it was renamed as the Apostolic Prefecture of Malakal; which was again promoted to the Diocese of Malakal on December 12, 1974.¹²

Presbyterian Mission in Malakal

The second Christian mission work in what was then the Upper Nile Province of Southern Sudan was begun by American Protestant missionaries, who established their mission at Dolieb Hill, on March 5, 1902, one year after the Catholic Mission at Lul.¹³ Dolieb Hill is a small town, situated at Sobat Revir, about twenty kilometers from Malakal.¹⁴ Two doctors, J. Kelly Giften and H. T. McLaughlin and their wives, started the mission. With them was an inhabitant of Dolieb Hill, from the Shilluk (Cholo) tribe, probably the third largest tribe among the eastern Nilotics in South Sudan.¹⁵

Seventh-day Adventist Mission in Malakal

The Adventist movement in Sudan started in 1956, in Khartoum, by an Egyptian couple who came as literature evangelists and who had first worked in Lebanon's capital, Beirut, at Middle East Division headquarters.¹⁶ In 1974 the Seventh-day Adventist Mission office was established in Khartoum.¹⁷ Given the operating context in Sudan then, it was not easy to spread the word of God due to

¹² Diocese of Malakal, South Sudan- GCatholic.org.

¹³ Ibid., 182.

¹⁴ Distance calculator, <https://www.distance.to/Malakal/Doleib-hill>.

¹⁵ Werner, Anderson, and Wheeler, *Day of Devastation*, 182.

¹⁶ Ibid., 363.

¹⁷ General Conference of Seventh-day Adventists, *Seventh-day Adventist Church Year Book, 1978*, <http://documents.adventistarchives.org/Yearbooks/YB1978.pdf>.

conflicts, together with the fact that Islam was dominant. However, the men of God did not slumber and continued the mission. In 1985, the SDA Church sent a pastor to Malakal. The purpose of establishing a church in Malakal was to enter the uncharted territories in Southern Sudan, based on the great commission Jesus gave to His followers.¹⁸

Malakal today hosts a mission office, which is coordinating the Seventh-day Adventist work in three states of the Greater Upper Nile Region of South Sudan. These are the Upper Nile, Unity, and Jonglei, with a membership in 2017 of 10,426. Of these, very few converts were from a Muslim background.¹⁹

¹⁸ Karst, Gerald D. "Light Breaks Over Sudan," *Mission: A Quarterly Report of World Mission*, April-June 1987: 20-22.

¹⁹ Office of Archives, Statistics, and Research, "Greater Upper Nile Field," *2019 Yearbook* (Silver Spring, MD: General Conference of Seventh-day Adventists, 2019), <https://www.adventistyearbook.org/entity?EntityID=42560&highlight=South|Sudan>.

CHAPTER 4

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OR POTENTIAL FOR WITNESSING TO MUSLIMS IN MALAKAL

Challenges for Witnessing to Muslims in Malakal

According to Dr. Børge Schantz, “There are theological, historical and sociological reasons” for Muslims to be resistant to the Gospel, but “the most important could well be the laws that limit religious liberty in Islamic nations, with the threat of execution for leaving Islam.”¹

Sharia

The Islamic law of apostasy, which requires execution by sword for an apostate man and life imprisonment for an apostate woman, is considered the most difficult hindrance to Christian witnessing to Muslims.² “Islam, from the earliest times and according to the teaching of the Koran, has always made it extremely easy to enter the Moslem brotherhood, and extremely difficult for those who once enter its fold to find exit.”³

¹ Børge Schantz, *Islam in the Post 9/11 World* (Grantham, England: Autumn House, 2003), 137.

² *Ibid.*, 46.

³ Samuel M. Zwemer, *The Law of Apostasy in Islam: Answering the Question Why there are Few Moslem Converts, and Giving Examples of their Moral Courage and Martyrdom* (London: Marshall Brothers, 2004), 18.

The following are some Quranic Ayahat (Verses) with the Muslim scholars' Tafsirs (Interpretation) and some quotations from Muslim traditional Hadith in support of the Muslim law on apostasy.

But those who reject faith after they accepted it and then go on adding to their defiance of faith never will their repentance be accepted; for they are those who have (of set purpose) gone astray. As to those who reject faith and die rejecting never would be accepted from any such as much gold as the earth contains though they should offer it for ransom. For such is (in store) a penalty grievous and they will find no helpers Surah 3 (Al-i'Imran): 90, 91.

They but wish that ye should reject faith as they do and thus be on the same footing (as they): but take not friends from their ranks until they flee in the way of Allah (from what is forbidden). But if they turn renegades seize them and slay them wherever ye find them; and (in any case) take no friends or helpers from their ranks Surah 4 (An-Nisaa): 89.

Some Zanadiqa (atheists) were brought to `Ali and he burnt them. The news of this event, reached Ibn `Abbas who said, "If I had been in his place, I would not have burnt them, as Allah's Messenger forbade it, saying, 'Do not punish anybody with Allah's punishment (fire).' I would have killed them according to the statement of Allah's Messenger 'Whoever changes his Islamic religion, then kill him.'"⁴

Attitudes and Prejudices of Muslims

In most cases, Muslims do not see the terms *Christian* and *Christianity* in a positive way. They do not view them in the same way as the Christians do. To become a Christian, according to the Muslim viewpoint, means rejecting one's people and uniting oneself with infidels or unbelievers. "To be Christian is to deny the One God, legalize prostitution, alcohol, gambling and pork eating, things that are considered offensive in Islam."⁵ For that reason Muslims see anyone who leaves

⁴Sahih al-Bukhari, 692; Book 88, *Hadith* 5, Vol. 9, Book 84, *Hadith* 57.

⁵Oscar Osindo, "Discipling Muslim Insiders: A Working Framework," *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 12 (2016): 222.

Islam as bringing shame, not only to his own household, but to the whole Islamic Community, and therefore Muslims see an urgent need to move “that object of shame.”⁶

Islam as Superior to Every Other Religion

Most Muslims believe that Islam is the “only true universal religion of God.”⁷

They also teach that all “true followers of Abraham and Moses, as well as those of Jesus and the rest, were all Muslims.”⁸

Azumah describes these feelings as follows:

From the very beginning of his ministry, Muhamad saw himself as in line with past prophets of the Judeo-Christian tradition. In the early stages of his Mission, he portrayed the Quran as the Arabic Version of the Jewish and the Christian Scriptures. In later stages, however, Islam was portrayed not just as a continuation but as the culmination of the Judeo-Christian tradition. Abraham, Moses, and Jesus (and his disciples) are portrayed in the Quran as Muslims. Jesus is presented as Muhammed’s forerunner, who announced the coming of the final and the only universal Prophet who brought the final and perfect revelation. Islam therefore considers itself the true Christianity (and the true Judaism). In other words, just as Christianity sees itself as the fulfillment and the replacement of Judaism, so Islam is the fulfillment and the replacement both Judaism and Christianity.⁹

Another issue that hinders mission among Muslims is a lack of knowledge regarding Islam on the part of Christian missionaries. It is almost impossible to win Muslims without at least basic knowledge about Islam.¹⁰ Muslims are not won in a

⁶Ibid.

⁷Hammudah ‘Abd-al-Ati, *Islam in Focus*, 3rd ed. (Beltsville, MD, Amana Publications, 1998), 10.

⁸Ibid., 25.

⁹Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 12, 13.

¹⁰Børge Schantz, *Your Muslim Neighbour and You* (Bracknell, Berkshire, England: Seventh-day Adventist Global Center for Islamic Studies, Berkshire, England, 1993), 7.

short period of normal acquaintances. Long-term friendship is needed to reach Muslims, and to break barriers, which separate Christians from Muslims.

William Miller quoted by Ray Roth, gives the following advice to those who are concerned with Muslims Evangelism:

Adventist laity should also become acquainted with some of the customs, beliefs, history, and practices of Islam. When they know something about Islam, they will be able to present Adventist teachings in a way that will be intelligible and attractive to Muslims. At the same time, they will be able to avoid misunderstandings.

Everyone concerned about evangelization of Muslims should read at least part of the Koran and also several of excellent books of Islam... if the laymen shows that he is knowledgeable of Islam, he can expect his Muslim friend to listen seriously.¹¹

Slow Growth Discouraging the Workers

Lack of quick results has discouraged many Christians from becoming involved in outreach to Muslims. Greg Livingstone, former director of the Arab World Ministries, in a book *Encountering the World of Islam*, discussed in detail the reasons which made pioneer work among Muslims fruitless. The following is a summary of what he discussed:

1. The antagonism that exists between indigenous Christians and Muslims. In many Muslim countries indigenous Christians are not in good relationship with Muslims.
2. Mistreatment of Muslims by colonial rulers has resulted in Muslim authorities preventing Christian mission work in their territories.

¹¹ Ray Roth, "Attitudes and Approaches to the Evangelization of Muslims in the Middle East," Doctor of Ministry dissertation, Andrews University, 1983, 133, 134, andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1220&context=dmin

3. “Traditionally, mission agencies have sent workers to countries that provided ‘Missionary Visas’.”¹² This caused a large majority of Christian missionaries to be sent to non-Muslim areas.
4. Missionaries have presented a foreign Christ to Muslims. “Historically, Christians have demanded that Muslims deny their cultures, causing them to dishonor their parents and families by not participating in Muslim observances and traditional family gatherings. Muslims have been less open to switch allegiance to a seemingly foreign Christ who rejects their culture and customs.”¹³
5. Unavailability of the Bible in the Muslim languages until recently.
6. Theological debates. “Over the centuries, most of the so-called witness to Muslims was no more than theological debate over the nature of Jesus, the Trinity, and the genuineness of Muhammad’s prophethood. Any questioning of Muhammad’s person or significance destroyed Muslims’ ability to hear objectively.”¹⁴
7. Politically motivated efforts to win Muslims.
8. Valuing Muslims’ friendship rather than being concerned for their spiritual needs.
9. Lack of friendship.
10. The Quran warns Muslims to stay away from Christians or they may go away from the true path of Islam.

¹² Greg Livingstone, “Why So Little Fruit?” in *Encountering the World of Islam*, ed. by Keith E. Swartley (Waynesboro, GA: Authentic Media, 2005), 326.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 326.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 327.

11. Language barriers.
12. Christian worship services in most Muslim countries are in foreign languages.
13. Lack of the gift of evangelism in the workers among Muslims.
14. Lack of face-to-face discipleship.¹⁵

Samuel Zwemer, A pioneer in Muslim mission, known as “the Apostle to Islam,” suggested the Muslim law regarding apostates as a major reason for lack of evangelism.

Many reasons are given for the paucity of converts. Some blame the church for lack of faith; others the missionaries for lack of love. The reason, others say, is that we have tried to win by controversy rather than by kindness, and our difficulty is one of method. Again, we are told that the time is not yet, the hour has not struck, the harvest is not ripe. In some cases, hope deferred has made the heart sick. “I venture the opinion,” wrote such a one, “that Islam is perhaps reprobate. Since the apostasy was subsequent to God’s offer of grace in Christ, He has withdrawn them from his sphere of activity. Perhaps *corporately* Islam has sinned against the Holy Spirit. I have toiled here two years, living in this Moslem home, thinking and talking like a Moslem, knowing their inner life as perhaps few do. Why is it, I wonder? To be quite candid, I expected that coming here in absolute simplicity and poverty, living amongst them, as near as possible as I believe Paul did, without committees or funds, I asked and expected God to give the increase, and yet, comparatively speaking, we have caught nothing.” Now all the reasons given above for the meagerness of direct results in work for Moslems have a measure of truth, yet none of them are sufficient. It is our conviction that among the many reasons for the small number of converts to the Christian faith in Moslem lands there is, perhaps, none so important, and yet concerning which so little is accurately known, as the Moslem law regarding apostates. Every convert to Christianity is an apostate from Islam, and although there have been apostates throughout all the centuries, and we know of cases even during the life-time of Mohammed the Prophet, the law of apostasy has become fixed in Islam, and for thirteen centuries has exercised its dread, if not its power, under all conditions and in every land. The apostate dies to his faith and is regarded by his family as worse than dead.¹⁶

¹⁵ Ibid., 328.

¹⁶ Zwemer, *The Law of Apostasy in Islam*, 16, 17.

Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament

The Muslim/Christian worldviews and beliefs have been in sharp disagreement since the emergence of Islam in Arabia and it seems this difference “outlives every generation.”¹⁷ This discourages many Christians from sharing their faith with Muslims. Following are the main issues: Muhammad, the supposed corruption of the Holy Scriptures, Jesus as the Son of God or Jesus’ divinity, the Trinity and, Jesus’ death and resurrection. The researcher will first point out Muslim arguments against these issues. I will also show how Christians should use these issues as bridges to communicate the Gospel to Muslims, instead of being blocks for Gospel outreach to Muslims.

Who Is Muhammad?

It is advisable at the beginning of friendship with a Muslim to carefully choose one’s words when confronted with the question of “Who is Muhammad?” Dealing diligently with that question will determine the type of relationship you will have afterward. Since Christians expect Muslims to respect Jesus, Muslims, as well, expect Christians to respect Muhammad and Islam.¹⁸ “There are those who totally refuse to talk about Muhammad, but when talking with a Muslim, it is very difficult, if not impossible, not to be confronted with the question, ‘What do you think of Mohammad?’ . . . Christians and Muslims alike cannot adequately address the subject

¹⁷ John Gilchrist, *Facing the Muslim Challenge: A Handbook of Christian-Muslim Apologetics* (Cape Town, South Africa: Life Challenge Africa, 2004), 5.

¹⁸ Swartley, *Encountering the World of Islam*, 278.

of Christian-Muslim relations without relating to the life of the prophet Muhammad.”¹⁹

Being a person who is ‘the most highly esteemed . . . in Islam,’ a Muslim ministry practitioner cannot escape dealing with the issue of the prophethood of Muhammad.” Christian scholars’ views differ in regard to Muhammad and Islam. Abner P. Dizon, Director of Philippine Frontier Missions (PFM) and Evangelism & Church Planting Institute (ECPI), mentioned in his article, “Issues in Adventist Muslim Ministry,” three basic schools of thought among Christian scholars: “the Critical school,” those who refer to Muhammad as a “False Prophet” and, Islam as “the religion of Anti-Christ”; “High contextual or bridge-building School,” whose views are based on Muslim’s beliefs and understanding, refer to Muhammad as “the Prophet for Muslims”; and Islam as “God’s revelation for Muslims.” Dr. Dizon, finally pointed out the third school as Progressive; in this, Muhammad is “compared to Protestant reformers like Luther and Calvin, but hardly with biblical prophets.”²⁰

Elder Ralph S. Watts, in an article with the title “Adventist Attitude toward Islam,” opposed the critical view, which saw Muhammad as “Anti-Christ” with a big “no.” He argued, “Seventh-day Adventists are sure from Biblical prophecy that this designation belongs to the ‘beast power’—the great apostate church of the Christian Era.” He further added: “when we take time to study the sayings of Muhammad we discover that he preached a message—an important message, by Seventh-day Adventist concepts which was, ‘Repent, for the judgment of God is at hand.’”²¹

¹⁹ Dizon, “Issues,” 9.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 9.

²¹ Ralph S. Watts, “The Attitude of Seventh-day Adventists Toward Islam, Muhammad Who was He?” Part 2, *Ministry* (July 1964): 7.

Elder Watts continued to reason that Muhammad’s message was preached to “the superstitious tribal people in Arabia, in order to warn and arouse them to the fear of God. In this respect we surely are not amiss in accepting Muhammad, as an instrument, a reformer, in the hand of God to awaken the masses to accept a religion far better than they had previously followed.”²²

Watts also noted that, being a religious dose not makes someone always right, people make mistakes unintentionally. “A man may be sincere, but mistaken. He may be honest in setting forth the true conception of God and yet not do it in the right way.”²³

Oscar Osindo, approaching Muhammad from a missiological viewpoint, stated that,

We should, first of all remember that it does not help to dismiss Muhammad as a non-entity, because a fifth of the world’s population listen to him. We should use Muhammad as one of our witnessing tools for he is the main ‘door keeper’ to hearts of million Muslims. Second, we should only judge Muhammad from the perspective and context of his time (seventh century A.D) rather than from a twenty-first century perspective. Third, it would be fair to compare Mohammad with Old Testaments prophets since it seems that Islam is an Old Testament type religion that developed in the post New Testament era. Perhaps if Muhammad had lived during the time of Joshua, or David, he would be more accepted as a true prophet. Fourth, we should take into consideration the overall had contribution Islam had made to civilization and how it preserved vital Christian documents during the time of the Dark Ages of Christianity. Fifth, we must always remember that the way to begin to relate to Muhammad and Muslims is not by arguing about whether Muhammad is a true or false prophet.²⁴

²² Ibid., 8.

²³ Ibid., 8.

²⁴ Osindo, *Relating to Muhammad*, 202.

Corruption of the Holy Scriptures

Although “the Quran frequently places a high value on the Bible and the ‘People of the book’” and there are only two verses in the Quran, which seem to support the idea of the corruption of the Torah and the Gospels, nevertheless, “almost all Muslims believe the Bible has been abrogated by the Quran.”²⁵ Surah 5 (Al-Ma’ida): 44 says that “We revealed the law (to Moses): therein was guidance and light.” Furthermore, in Surah 5:46 we read: “And therein we sent Jesus, Son of Mary, confirming the Law that had come before him: We sent him the Gospel: therein was guidance and the light.”

Surah 5(Al- Ma’ida):68 reads: “Say: ‘O people of the Book! You have no ground to stand unless ye stand fast by the Law, and the Gospel and all the revelation that come to you from the Lord.’”

Surah 4 (An- Nisa’a): 136 continues: “O ye who believe! Believe in God and His Apostle and the scripture, which He hath sent to His Apostle and the scripture which He hath sent to those before (him). Any who denieth God, His angels, His Books, His Apostle, and the Day of Judgment, hath gone far, far astray.”

Finally, Surah 2 (Al- Baqara): 136 notes: “We believe in Allah, and the revelation given to us, and to Abraham, Isma’il, Isaac, Jacob, and the Tribes, and that given to Moses and Jesus, and that given to [all] prophets from their Lord: We make no difference between one and another of them: And we bow to Allah [in Islam].”

Abiyah Akbar, in his book *Sharing Your Faith with a Muslim*, argued against the corruption of the Bible with the following points:

²⁵ Parshall, *Muslim Evangelism*, 146.

1. The strange teaching about the corruption of the Bible was invented by Muslims a “century after their Prophet,” and has no basis in the Quran.
2. The Qur’an accuses bad Jews of changing the Scripture by their mouths.
3. Muslims accused Jews and Christians who cannot agree, whatever the case, to change the Scripture.
4. It is not possible to corrupt all the copies worldwide without one original copy remaining.
5. Such a big event cannot occur unrecorded in history either by friends or enemies.
6. There were Jewish and Christian scholars who joined Islam, like Abdullah b. Salam. They could have kept the original copy of the corrupted books with
7. them, in support of their new faith, as previously done by Jews who joined Christianity.²⁶

Jesus

In Islam, Jesus, as well as his mother Mary are highly regarded.²⁷ They are the only human beings, “whom the Quran describes as sinless (3:36, 46).”²⁸ Meanwhile, others, including the prophets are considered as “falling into temptation, sinning and asking for forgiveness: Adam (7:22-23), Abraham (26:82), Moses (28:16), Jonah (37:142) and Muhammad (3:31; 47:19).”²⁹ Islam not only accepts Jesus as a historical

²⁶Abdiyah Akbar Abdul-Haqq, *Sharing Your Faith with a Muslim*, (Minneapolis, MN: Bethany House, 1980), 36-38.

²⁷ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 100.

²⁸ Ibid., 106.

²⁹ Ibid., 107.

figure, “but also as one of the most distinguished messengers of God.”³⁰ This recognizes His miraculous birth by the Virgin Mary and being among the nearest to God: “Behold! The angels said “O Mary! Allah giveth thee glad tidings of a Word from Him: his name will be Christ Jesus the son of Mary held in honor in this world and the Hereafter and of (the company of) those nearest to Allah.” Surah 3 (Ali’-Imran): 45.

Al-Masih Isa, in the Muslim religion, “is the only one, apart from God, with the power to create life (birds) by using clay and breathing life into them” (3:49).³¹

Jesus as Son of God

In general, Muslims consider the biblical teaching about Jesus Christ as the Son of God, as a literal, physical, biological birth. This required God to have Mary as a physical wife, and resulted in the biological birth of the Son, Jesus Christ. The Quran argues:

He is the Originator of the heavens and the earth. How can He have children when He has no wife? Surah 3 (Ali’- Imran): 45.

And exalted be the Majesty of our Lord, He has taken neither a wife, nor a son. Surah 72 (Al-Jinn): 3.

Say: He is God, the One and Only; God, the Eternal, Absolute; He begetteth not, nor is He begotten; and there is none like unto Him. Surah 112 (Al-Ikhlās): 1-4.

It is not befitting to (the majesty of) God that He should beget a son. Glory be to Him! When He determines a matter, He only says to it, ‘Be,’ and it is. Surah 19 (Maryam): 35.

They say: “(God) Most Gracious has begotten a son! Indeed, ye have put forth a thing most monstrous! At it the skies are ready to burst, the earth to split asunder, and the mountains to fall down in utter ruin, that they should invoke a

³⁰ Abd-al-Ati, *Islam in Focus*, 51.

³¹ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 107.

son for [Allah] Most Gracious. For it is not consonant with the majesty of (God) Most Gracious that He should beget a son.” Surah 19 (Maryam): 88-92.

The following Muslim scholars’ comments on the above-mentioned verses show strongly their misconceptions of the biblical teaching about the sonship of Jesus Christ:

It is only rational to say that a child is one born of male and female, of the same kind and nature, and Allah is far above homogeneousness.”... “A child must be born of male and female, and it cannot be that Allah has a consort and a child. It is he who has created all things and if there is nothing except that which Allah has created. How could he have a son?”³²

“Begetting a son is a physical act depending on the need of men’s animal nature. God Most High is independent of all needs, and it is derogatory to Him to attribute such an act to Him. It is merely a relic of pagan and anthropomorphic superstitions. Such an attribution to God of a material nature, and of the lower animal functions of sex is derogatory to the dignity and glory of God. The belief in God begetting a son is not a question of words or of speculative thought. It is a stupendous blasphemy against God. It lowers God to the level of an animal.”³³

“Their heresy suggests that Allah had a consort and a son by her, and is obviously rejected by the Qur’an.”³⁴

It is unfortunate that some Muslim scholars, based on few Quranic verses misunderstood the Bible teaching about the begotten son of God, Jesus Christ, and gave it a literal meaning. However, “No Christian believes that the word begotten, when referring to Jesus, is to be taken in human or literal sense. The Bible deals with spiritual subjects but uses human terminology to describe spiritual relationships. The words father, son, and the begotten must be viewed as figurative and metaphysical.”³⁵

³² Abd al-Fadi, “The Sonship of Christ in The Qur’an,” *The Person of Christ in the Gospel and the Quran* (2010), 25-26, https://info1.sermon-online.com/english/TheGoodWay/The_Person_Of_Christ_In_The_Gospel_And_The_Koran_1975.doc.

³³ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 104.

³⁴ Abd al-Fadi, “The Sonship of Christ,” 26.

³⁵ Parshall, *Muslim Evangelism*, 158.

The following Bible texts show the figurative use of the word “son of God” in the Bible, not only for Jesus, but also for believers.

Regarding his Son, who as to his Human nature was a descendant of David, and who through the Spirit of holiness was declared with power to be the son of God by his resurrection from dead: Jesus Christ Our Lord. (Rom 1: 3, 4)

Yet to all who received him, to those who believe in his name he gave them right to become the Children of God—children born not of natural descendant, nor of human decision or husband’s will, but born of God. (John 1:12, 13)

He predestined us to be adopted as his Sons through Jesus Christ, in accordance with his pleasure and will. (Eph 1:5)

Because those who are led by the Holy Spirit are call the Sons of God. (Rom 8:14)

Interestingly, the use of the word son (*Ibn*) in Arabic language is not limited to biological birth; it is sometimes figurative. The following are examples of the Arabic figurative used for the word son (*Ibn*): Ibn Al-sabil, “which literally means son of road.”³⁶ The phrase *Ibn Al-sabil*, fortunately enough is mentioned in five Quranic Suras: Surah 8 (Al-anfal):41; Surah 9 (At-Tauba):60; Surah 17 (Bani Isra-il):26; Surah 30 (Ar-Rum):38; Surah 59 (Al- Hashr):7. None of the Arabic speaking people can accept that a road married and had a son. It really means: “A wayfarer, a wanderer, a passerby, or a traveler.”³⁷ Ibn Nil (Son of Nile) is mostly used by Sudanese and Egyptian brothers who are connected by the Nile.³⁸ Ibn Aharb (son of war) means *the warrior*. Ibn al Lial (son of the night), which means *the thief*.³⁹ Nevertheless,

³⁶ Ibid., 158.

³⁷ Keith E. Swartley, *Encountering the World of Islam*, 285.

³⁸ Gerhard Nehls, and Walter Eric, *Christian-Islamic Controversy* (Nairobi, Kenya: Life Challenge Africa, 2010), 84.

³⁹ Munir Baalbaki, *Al Mawrid: A Modern Arabic-English Dictionary*, 29th ed. (Beirut, Lebanon: Dar El-lim Lil Malayen, 1995), 26.

The Islamic position seems to have been influenced by the pre-Islamic Arab belief that God had daughters in the form of female deities whose intercession was sought. In fact, the Qur'anic denials of God having children were first directed at the pre-Islamic Arabs, who are accused of preferring sons for themselves, but assuming that God only has daughters (53:19-22). It appears that these denials were then extended to the Christian teaching about Jesus being the Son of God without a good understanding of what Christians mean by that title. Unfortunately, this position remains the orthodox Muslim teaching regardless of Christian protestations to the contrary.⁴⁰

The Trinity

The Issue of the Trinity has been among the “major stumbling blocks” in Christian outreach to the Muslims. “Muslims accuse the Christians of worshipping three Gods, God the Father, Mary the Mother, and Jesus Christ the Son.”⁴¹ Since Muslims believe that “the Quran is eternal and uncreated, and God is eternal and uncreated,’ it may help to ask your Muslim friend if they had two Gods since the Quran and God are coeternal and co-uncreated, according to their belief. Nevertheless it is good to bear in mind that,⁴² “the doctrine of the Trinity is extremely difficult and it is not well understood by ordinary Christians.’ There is an element of mystery in God’s becoming man. An element of mystery that surpasses the intellect and carries us into realm of naked faith.”⁴³ Keith E. Swartley, in the book, *Encountering the World of Islam*, added that “our friends [Muslims] may have great difficulty understanding the Trinity, thinking we worship three gods. Rather than becoming mired in a vain argument, we can assure them that we believe God is one, and continue to pray that, over time, God will help them discern this concept. Indeed, the

⁴⁰ Azumah. *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 104.

⁴¹ Pope Shenunda III, *Trinity and Unity*, Lecture delivered at the Cathedral of Mark in Cairo 2010, 2, <http://www.the-good-way.com>.

⁴² Swartley, *Encountering the World of Islam*, 285.

⁴³ Parshall, *Muslim Evangelism*, 157.

doctrine of the Trinity is difficult even for Christians to understand, so we certainly do not want to make that a condition for friendship with Muslims.”⁴⁴

Jesus’ Death, Crucifixion and Resurrection

“The Muslim believes that Jesus was neither killed nor crucified, but God raised him up to Himself in honor and grace.”⁴⁵ And in the following is the Qur’anic support, “That they said [in boast], “We killed Christ Jesus the son of Mary, the Messenger of Allah”; but they killed him not, nor crucified him, but so it was made to appear to them, and those who differ therein are full of doubts, with no [certain] knowledge, but only conjecture to follow, for of a surety they killed him not:- Nay, Allah raised him up unto Himself” Surah 4 (An-Nisa):157-158.

According to Dr. John Azuumah, almost all Muslims who comment on the above mentioned verses agreed that a crucifixion happened, but Jesus was not the One crucified. The two points most debated were the meaning of the word “appears,” and who was crucified. In the following, Dr. Azumah listed the possibilities suggested by Muslim commentaries:

1. God confused the Jews to see all of Jesus’ disciples to look like him, at the time of Jesus’ arrest, and captured one of them and crucified him instead of Jesus.
2. Simon of Cyrene accepted voluntarily to replaces him on cross.
3. Jesus himself had bribed Sergus, one of his disciples, with the promise of the paradise; he then took Jesus’ place.

⁴⁴ Swartley, *Encountering the World of Islam*, 269.

⁴⁵ Abd-al-Ati, *Islam in Focus*, 122.

4. God made Judas to look like Jesus, and was crucified as the price of his betrayal.
5. God fooled the Jews “by taking Jesus to heaven, For the Jews to cover up the event of Jesus’ ascension, they captured any an innocent man, who was victimized in a remote area. They then prevented any one to come to the area until his body decayed and could not be recognized.
6. Pilate commanded his soldiers to release Jesus Barabbas, but unknowingly released Jesus of Nazareth, who then fled to where his disciples were assembling.

Furthermore, Azumah stated that, “Islamic denials of Jesus’ death are complicated by the existence of other Qur’anic verses that allude to his death.” Here are some of these verses: Surah 19 (Maryam): 33 “So peace is on me the day I was born, the day that I die, and the day that I shall be raised up to life [again].” Surah 3 (Ali-i-Imran): 55 “Behold! Allah said: “O Jesus! I will take thee and raise thee to Myself and clear thee [of the falsehoods] of those who blaspheme; I will make those who follow thee superior to those who reject faith, to the Day of Resurrection: Then shall ye all return unto me, and I will judge between you of the matters wherein ye dispute.”

Mainstream Islamic teaching has continued to maintain that all references to the death of Jesus in the Qur’an are eschatological (that is, they refer to his death forty years after his second coming). However, some individual Muslim commentators and writers have acknowledged that 3:55 and 3:48 may refer to a real death of Jesus. Some have said that Jesus died for three hours before being raised, others that he was dead for seven hours. Ibn Kathir (died 1373) simply said, ‘God caused him to die for three days, then resurrected him, then raised him.’⁴⁶

⁴⁶ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 112-114

Fear of Persecution

About ninety-five percent of the new converts from Muslim background to Christianity “tell stories of the ill-treatment by their families within days of revealing their intention ‘to become a Christian.’”⁴⁷

Disunity among the Gospel Experts in Muslim Ministry

Disunity among the laborers in Muslim Ministries, according, to Abner P. Dizon, has prevented the Seventh-day Adventist Church from embracing Muslim Ministries. Dizon further says that the lack of unity not only exists among Adventist workers in Muslim Ministries, but also is a “Global Christian Community” phenomenon. Since Adventists did not inherit new approaches from Evangelicals, “but also the current missiological debate over the C4 and C5 approaches,” Dr. Dizon advised that

Adventist Muslim ministry practitioners should never turn a blind eye on issues where Islam departs from or even contradicts the teachings of the Bible. If we become totally like Muslims in our regard for Islam then we are in danger of fitting the description of the blind who “lead the blind” (Luke 6:39) and we will all fall into the ditch!⁴⁸

Opportunities for Witnessing to Muslims in Malakal

Social Connections between Christians and Muslims in Malakal

In South Sudan, as well as in some other parts of Moslem countries, “Muslims and Christians have often lived as close relations and neighbors. At the grass-roots level, they have on the whole lived in peace. Muslim relatives and friends visit

⁴⁷Dizon, “*Issues*,” 5.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, 2, 4.

Christians at Christmas to wish them well, and Christians in turn visit their Muslim friends and relatives during Islamic festivals. On these occasions, gifts and meals are shared. At weddings and child-naming ceremonies, and even at the ordination of priests, Muslims are known to come to church, and Christians attend Muslim gatherings when a ceremony involves a friend or relative.”⁴⁹ But still Christians are reluctant to share the gospel with Muslim relatives, friends, and work colleagues.

Muslims and the Three Angels’ Messages

From the early stages of its mission, the Seventh-day Adventist Church distinguished itself by presenting “the urgent end-time truths of the eternal gospel” to all humankind, as foretold by John the Revelator: “Then I saw another angel flying in midair, and he had the eternal gospel to proclaim to those who live on the earth—to every nation, tribe, language and people. He said in a loud voice, ‘Fear God and give him glory, because the hour of his judgment has come. Worship him who made the heavens, the earth, the sea and the springs of water’” (Rev 14: 6, 7).

According to Neal C. Wilson, former world president of the Adventist Church, “no people are excluded from the universal purpose of God, none fall outside the promise, and none are beyond the reach of the gospel—neither Jew nor Greek nor Muslim.”⁵⁰

“For there is no difference between Jew and Gentile—the same Lord is Lord of all and richly blesses all who call on him, for, ‘Everyone who calls on the name of the Lord will be saved.’” (Romans 10: 12, 13)

⁴⁹Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 7.

⁵⁰ Neal C Wilson, “Foreword,” *The Three Angels and the Crescent: A reader, Adventist Approaches to Islamic People*, by Jonquil Hole and Børge Schanz (Bracknell, Berkshire: SDA Global Center for Islamic Studies, 1993), 7.

The Gospel Commission

God sent Abram, who later became Abraham the Father of all nations, as the first missionary.⁵¹ The Scriptures record the first mission command as directed to Abram, “Go from your country, your people and your father’s household to the land I will show you. I will make you into a great nation, and I will bless you; I will make your name great, and you will be a blessing. I will bless those who bless you, and whoever curses you I will curse; and all peoples on earth will be blessed through you.” (Gen 12:1–3)

After that, Jacob, who was renamed Israel, was chosen to be “a light to the Gentiles” and to take God’s salvation “to the ends of the earth” (Isa 49: 6). Jonah was later sent to warn Assyria of the coming judgment upon Nineveh (Jonah 1:2).

In the New Testament, the resurrected Christ mandated His followers in all ages to take the good news of his resurrection to the “end of the earth” (Matt 28:18-20; Mark 16:15, 17; Luke 24:48, 49; John 20:21; Acts 1:8). Jesus also invited His disciples to follow Him and make them “Fishers of Men” (Mark 1:17).

People cannot believe unless they hear, and they cannot hear without a preacher (Rom 10: 14, 15). “And this gospel of the kingdom will be preached in the whole world as a testimony to all nations, and then the end will come” (Matt 24:14).

There is more blessing in giving than receiving (Acts 20: 35). When the Church neglects to reach out, it risks its very own life. The apostle Paul once cried out, “For when I preach the gospel, I cannot boast, since I am compelled to preach. Woe to me if I do not preach the gospel!” (1 Cor 9:16). Mission is central to our identity. Jesus did not create the Church and then give it mission as one of its tasks.

⁵¹ Børge Schantz and Steven Thompson, *Biblical Missionaries* (Nampa, ID: Pacific Press, 2015), 23.

The divine sending plan comes prior to the church. “Mission gives birth to the Church and is its mother. The very essence or nature of the Church is mission. If the Church ceases to be missionary, it has not simply failed in its task, but has actually ceased being the Church. It becomes only a religiously oriented social organization.”⁵²

Witnessing requires only basic knowledge and personal experience (Luke 8: 39).

“From everyone who has been given much, much will be demanded; and from the one who has been entrusted with much, much more will be asked” (Luke 12:48b).

According to Dr. Lyle VanderWerff,

One of the factors prompting the rise of Islam was that the Church had ‘neglected Arabia.’ . . . The deserts and cities of Arabia had been passed over by churches that fail to realize the spiritual hunger the predecessors and contemporaries of Muhammad. . . . Although it is known that some of Muhammad’s earliest disciples embraced Christianity after fleeing to Ethiopia. However, the heartland of Arabia received only the heretical, fringe expression of that faith, leaving Muhammad still seeking.⁵³

God’s Example of Mission and Self-Sacrificing Service

God is the initiator of mission as is clearly seen in the Holy Scriptures. For example, in the Old Testament book of Genesis, He came to Adam and Eve after their fall into sin. And afterwards He revealed himself to Abram, who later became Abraham, the father of nations. Furthermore, in the book of Exodus, God instructed the prophet Moses to build a sanctuary for Him to live among His people, the Israelites. God’s coming to His people is also seen in the New Testament, embodied in the ministry of our Lord and Savior Jesus Christ who is Emanuel, “God with U

⁵² John L. Dybdahl, ed., *Adventist Mission in the 21st Century: The Joys and Challenges of Presenting Jesus to a Diverse World* (Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald, 1999), 17, 18, 60, 61.

⁵³ Lyle VanderWerff, “Mission Lessons from History,” in *Encountering the World of Islam*, 329.

Although God can reveal Himself to His people directly, He has chosen human agents to do mission.

According to Schantz and Thompson,

The biblical picture of God, from Genesis to Revelation, focuses on His initiative in finding and saving His people. He came to Adam and Eve, He came to Abram, and He came to live with His people of Israel in the Sanctuary. The theme of the coming God is repeated across the Old Testament and especially into the New, in the ministry of Jesus Christ. Even in the New Testament, however, the coming of God Himself is still expected. “I am the Alpha and the Omega,” says the Lord God, “who is, and who was, and who is to come” (Revelation 1: 8). Today, God comes to people groups of this world through the persons of His followers. Through them God continue to ‘walk’ among the nations, using the feet of His human agents. He demonstrates His unfailing love for all humanity through the ministry, Crucifixion, resurrection, and heavenly ministry of Jesus Christ. He appeals to human hearts today through the presence of the Holy Spirit. He will send His son Jesus Christ back to this earth at the end of this age to rescue all who have return to Him. In the meantime, God still recruits humans, including us, to share His Mission.⁵⁴

Burden for the Lost

If it is possible to write Jesus’ mission statement, the best could be his very words: “For the Son of man came to seek and to save the lost” (Luke 19: 10).⁵⁵

All Jesus’ activities on earth was motivated by the passion for lost souls.

The Holy Scriptures described Jesus’ actions as walking “through all the towns and villages, teaching in their synagogues, preaching the good news of the kingdom and healing every disease and sickness. When he saw the crowds he had compassion on them, because they were harassed and helpless, like sheep without a shepherd (Matt 9: 35, 36).

⁵⁴ Schantz and Thompson, *Biblical Missionaries*, 20, 21.

⁵⁵ John M. Fowler, *Adult Sabbath School Bible Study Guide, The Book of Luke*, 2nd quarter, 2015(Nairobi, Kenya, Africa Herald publishing House), 23.

According to Dr. Ray Roth,

Seventh-day Adventists should continue to pray and labor for the salvation of Muslims because of the value in God's sight of every man, woman, and child whom he has created. It is sometime erroneously supposed that Missionary effort is justified only when large numbers of people are converted. Certainly Christ desires the salvation of ' a great multitude which no man could number' (Rev 7:9). If Christ left the ninety-nine in order to find and save one lost sheep, can we be justified in doing less? Christ said there was joy in heaven over one sinner who repents. Then if only one Muslim were saved as result of a century of Christian effort, would not this effort have been Justified?⁵⁶

Islam's Shortcomings toward Meeting Human Needs

One of the main reasons that urge Gospel outreach to Muslims is that Islam fails to pay attention to the issue of sin and redemption. In Islam, humans are "born in natural state of purity or *fit rah* [and] . . . whatever becomes of man after birth is the result of external influence and intruding factors."⁵⁷ Thus, there is no need for a Redeemer or redemption, and no guarantee of forgiveness. As William Miller notes:

Islam fails to diagnose man's condition as a sinner unable to know and obey God perfectly, it fails to reveal God in His holiness and his love for sinful men, it fails to give the sinner assurance of forgiveness and peace with God, and it fails to supply the Holy Spirit to teach and guide and sanctify the believer. It points men to a dead prophet and not to the Lord Jesus, who conquered death and is alive.⁵⁸

According to Bethmann, the concept of sin and redemption from it is the deepest rift between Christianity and Islam. "Naturally, as there is no deep conviction of sin in Islam, no feeling of an estrangement between God and man, there is no need

⁵⁶ Ray Roth, "Attitudes and Approaches to the Evangelization of Muslims in the Middle East," Doctor of Ministry dissertation, Andrews University, 1983, 144, [145 andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1220&context=dmin](http://andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1220&context=dmin).

⁵⁷ Abd-al-Ati, *Islam in Focus*, 28.

⁵⁸ William McElwee Miller, *A Christian's Response to Islam* (Phillipsburg, NJ: Presbyterian and Reformed, 1979), 160-161.

for reconciliation, no need for redemption, nor for a Saviour from sin, no need for a complete turn in life, nor for being born again in the likeness of the spirit. And here lies the deepest gulf which separates Christianity from Islam.”⁵⁹

Islam Is a Missionary Religion

“Islam is a missionary religion, and the only religion that poses a serious missionary challenge to Christianity.”⁶⁰ William Wagner, in his book *How Islam Plans to Change the World*, claims that Islam and Christianity both have well-defined philosophies as well as fully thought out methodologies on how to make a difference in the world. He explains that

Both see their faith as worldwide faith, although their areas of strength are localized.

Both see their sources of their communication as issuing from their Holy Book, which gives support to their position.

Both have Mission organizations have as their main purpose the furtherance their faith.

Both see conversion to their belief as a positive aspect of their actions.

Both see the actions of other as satanic and have some fear of the other’s successes.

Both Christianity and Islam are ‘fractured religions’ which have many different expressions and theologies. This plurality carries over to mission and *Da’wah*.

Both are aware of the paradigm shift taking place worldwide and feel there is a spiritual vacuum that they can fill.

Both see Eastern Europe as a fertile field for expansion.

Both extend a call for people to enter into a broad community of believers, Christians into the kingdom of God and Muslims into the *ummah*.⁶¹

⁵⁹ E. W. Bethmann, *Bridge to Islam: A Study of the Religious Forces of Islam and Christianity in the Near East* (Nashville, TN: Southern Publishing Association, 1950), 30.

⁶⁰ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 13.

⁶¹ William Wagner, *How Islam Plans to Change the World* (Grand Rapids MI: Kregel, 2004), 45.

It is also very interesting to know that both the Christian Scripture and Islamic books contain the orders for their followers are to be involved in proclamation of their faith. Here are two examples:

Go then, to all peoples everywhere and make them my disciples: baptize them in the name of the father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit, and teach them to obey everything I have commanded you. And I will be with you always, to the end of the age. (Matt 28: 19-20, GNT)

Thus have we made of you an Umma justly balanced, that ye might be witnesses over nations and the apostle a witness over you Surah 2 (Al-Baqara): 143.

Islam has a clear mission strategy to change the world and it is to be accomplished mainly through three elements, according to William Wagner:

Dawah – the Islamic equivalent to Christian Mission
Jihad – holy war
The Mosque – their physical presence.⁶²

These three elements—*Dawah*, *Jihad*, and the Mosque—are discussed in the following sections.

Da'wah

Dawah from, Arabic word “*dah'u*,” means “to invite or call.”

According to William Wanger, “*deai*,” “which is the nearest Islamic equivalent of Christian missionary or mission worker” and could be possibly described “as a preacher or a worker in Islam,” had duties to the following people:

To himself
To one's family
To one's neighbors
To one's fellow citizens
To one's country men
To one's fellow human beings.⁶³

⁶²Ibid.

⁶³ Wagner, *How Islam Plans*, 40.

Jihad

The word *Jihad* is derived from the Arabic root which means, “struggle or strive.” “This struggle can be “both spiritual and military.”⁶⁴ Although *Jihad* is mostly associated with war, it can be “against Allah and his teachings. It is the struggle in one’s own heart to follow the will of Allah and is an internal battle for righteousness. The lesser *jihad* is what we know as the traditional holy war that is declared in the name of Allah and is used to spread his will. While all Muslims must undertake the greater *jihad*, not all are required to participate in the lesser *jihad*, but they must support it when it does occur.”⁶⁵

On this topic, Azumah writes:

The struggle in the cause of God is of three kinds. The first is the struggle against a visible (human) enemy. The second is the struggle against the temptation of the Devil. The third is the struggle against one’s own passions. While carrying on a jihad, Muslims must strive with their time, knowledge, energy, possessions, talents, and all their resources for the cause of God. This is the true meaning of *jihad*, which was commanded by Allah, and expounded of the Holy prophet, for the faithful to follow. It has a much broader meaning than fighting in battle.⁶⁶

Mosque

In an Islamic setting, a mosque occupies an essential place, whether religiously or culturally. Since the time of Muhammad’s successors, the Caliphs, “the mosque continued to function as a religio-political center. . . . The mosque can also function as a hall of assembly, a school, parliament, and

⁶⁴ Ibid., 67.

⁶⁵ Ibid., 67, 68.

⁶⁶ Azumah, *My Neighbour’s Faith*, 38, 39.

place for worship. Two types of worship take place in a mosque: the five daily times of ritual prayers, and weekly *Juma'a* (Friday) Prayers.”⁶⁷

⁶⁷ Osindo, *Relating to Muhammad*, 200.

CHAPTER 5

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section of the study presents the methodological strategies used to gather data from the Seventh-day Adventist members as respondents to the research question in order to meet the objectives of the study. The researcher conducted a field-based study to collect reliable and valid information that will be useful in developing a suitable strategy to be used by the members of the Seventh-day Adventist Church to reach out to the Muslim community, which includes their neighbors and friends in Malakal. The strategy employed was intended to motivate them, without the fear of rejection or to be harmed by the recipient of the gospel. This approach was chosen because the church has not invested much in the field of witnessing among the Muslim communities in Malakal.

Research Design

This study used the qualitative approach to gather information from the active members of the Seventh-day Adventist church in Malakal. The study applied a descriptive research design to describe the situation as it was at the time of the study.

Study Location and Population

The study was conducted in Malakal, the commercial capital of Central Upper Nile State. In spite of the Muslim and Christian community coexisting in this area for many years without any problem, Christians have not been able to evangelize much

among the Muslim communities, as evidenced in the steady growth of the Islamic faith.

Sample

In the study, only active Adventist members (evangelists, pastors, church elders, and directors) were involved. In this case, the study managed to gather data from 68 active church members. The study used purposive sampling so that only respondents who met the eligibility criteria to be interviewed in this study were involved.

Data Collection Methods and Instruments

The method of data collection used was a survey using a self-administered questionnaire for the respondents from the different Adventist churches. The researcher chose this instrument because it was time and cost effective and also provided a sense of physical evidence. Thus, the researcher was able to collect much data within a very short time.

The questionnaire was set up carefully prepared and logically ordered, based on the variables and the research objectives. It consisted of an introductory part that introduced the researcher to the respondent, including the name of the researcher, the name of Middle East University, where the researcher was studying, and the purpose of the study. The questionnaire contained three sections. Section A of the questionnaire included general information of respondents like gender, and length of church membership. Section B involved objective answering of questions (quantitative data through closed-ended questions). Section C involved respondents' views and suggestions (qualitative information through open-ended questions).

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to conducting the data collection, the researcher established community entry with the local authority by seeking ethical clearance in Malakal. Because Malakal covers a wide area, the researcher identified each church and then requested the names of active evangelists, pastors, elders, and directors in each Adventist church, and compiled the names in a list, which guided him in identifying the respondents.

Data Organization and Analysis

This section was concerned with organizing and presenting the data collection.

Editing

Detecting and eliminating errors and keeping them to a minimum in the completed questionnaire. This helped the researcher to check for completeness of answers in each the questionnaire.

Coding

This process of assigning numerals or other symbols to answers was done so that responses could be put into a limited number of classes and categories. This was done on all sections of quantitative questionnaires and open-ended questions, which had similar answers.

Tabulation

This involved the data being arranged in a logical order for the purpose of statistical analysis and was done by the researcher after sorting the data and knowing the number of tables required. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis

The researcher used SPSS because it can perform complex data manipulation and analysis and has many statistical and mathematical functions. Objectives 1 and 2 were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher considered four ethical issues during the data collection phase as follows:

Protection from Harm

Before embarking on the interview process, the researcher introduced himself and the research assistants to the local authorities in Malakal. In a similar way, during the data collection process the researcher and research assistants introduced themselves to the respondent. This was followed by ensuring that data collection was conducted in a safe and secure environment without making the respondent feeling uncomfortable. The information that a respondent shared was handled with extra care to ensure that it was secured safely and no one had access to the information without the respondent's informed consent.

Informed Consent

The researcher designed an informed consent form that was given to the respondent after the introduction had been done by the researcher and the research assistant. The respondents were asked to read all the questions on the informed consent. After reading the questions, the respondents were asked whether he/she had understood the questions. If needed, clarification was provided by the researcher on the issues of interest. Later the respondent was asked to sign the informed consent on

a voluntary basis to participate in the interview. In case the respondent was not willing to take part, he/she was not coerced to sign the informed consent.

Confidentiality

To ensure confidentiality, the researcher used pseudonyms on every questionnaire. This also helped to distinguish the response of different respondents.

Right to Privacy

The researcher respected the rights of the respondent by collecting data in the places chosen by them which in most cases was at the local churches.

CHAPTER 6

RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

This chapter presents results of the research on barriers to sharing the Gospel with Muslim friends in Malakal.

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The study investigated the demographic characteristics of the respondents in terms of gender and how long they have held church membership. The findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	52	76.5
	Female	16	23.5
Church Membership	Less than 1 year	8	11.8
	1-5 years	12	17.6
	6-10 years	21	30.9
	11-15 years	17	25.0
	16 or more years	10	14.7
	Total	68	100.0

Results show that 52 (77%) of the respondents were male, while only 16 (23%) were female. This shows the dominance of male members in the administration (pastors, evangelists, church leaders, etc.) in the Adventist Church.

Results indicate that over half of the church administrators/workers 38 (56%) had been members of the Adventist church for 6-15 years, with those having less than a year accounting for only 12% of the members consulted. This shows how long most of the respondents had been working for the Adventist Church.

Major Strategies Used by the Adventist Church to Share the Gospel with Muslims

The main objective was to investigate major strategies used by Adventist Church leaders and members to share the Gospel with their Muslim neighbors or friends. The variable investigated was major strategies used by the Adventist Church. The results are presented in terms of frequency and percentage in Table 2, which presents empirical information on strategies used by Adventist Church to share the Gospel with the Muslim neighbors or friends.

Table 2: Major Adventist strategies for sharing the Gospel with Muslims

Items	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Never
House to house evangelism	3 (4.4%)	12 (17.6%)	43 (63.2%)	10 (14.7%)
Person to person evangelism	3 (4.4%)	20 (29.4%)	40 (58.8%)	5 (7.4%)
Public evangelism in villages	10 (14.7%)	36 (52.9%)	16 (23.5%)	6 (8.8%)
Public evangelism in urban areas	16 (23.5%)	26 (38.2%)	22 (32.4%)	4 (5.9%)
Missionary strategy	10 (14.7%)	34 (50.0%)	23 (33.8%)	1 (1.5%)
Use of Adventist learning institutions	9 (13.2%)	27 (39.7%)	24 (35.3%)	8 (11.8%)
Use of extreme media (TV, radio, newspapers)	4 (5.9%)	21 (30.9%)	36 (52.9%)	7 (10.3%)
Use of social media	4 (5.9%)	18 (26.5%)	31 (45.6%)	15 (22.1%)
Use of the testimonies	3 (4.4%)	31 (45.6%)	34 (50%)	0 (0%)

House-to-House Evangelism

The results indicate that 3 (4.4%) of the Adventist respondents said house-to-house evangelism is very often used, 12 (17.6%) felt that it was often used, 43 (63.2%) felt that it is sometimes used, and 10 (14.7%) had the feeling that it was never used to share the gospel with Muslims. This implies that house-to-house strategy is not much used and if effectively used might help the church to communicate the Gospel to the Muslims, hence increasing the conversion rate of Muslims to Adventism in Malakal. A majority (40 or 58.8%) of the respondents felt that it was sometimes used and therefore efforts are required to make the strategy efficient, as it can help the Adventist Church communicate more about the Gospel to Muslims in Malakal.

Public Evangelism in Villages

Findings indicate that the Adventist Church often uses public evangelism in the villages; the majority, 36 (52.9%), accepted that this is a good effort, though it seems that many churches do not apply it efficiently or effectively. It is good to suggest that the Adventist Church needs to put more effort into this, and embrace public evangelism in villages as well as in urban areas

Findings indicate that a majority, 26 (38.2%) of the Adventist members accepted that public evangelism in urban areas is often used, though the statistics show that 22 (32.4%) and 4 (5.9%) felt that it was only sometimes or never used. In this case, the results imply that not all Adventist members were satisfied with the level in which public evangelism is used in the urban area in Malakal, and more efforts are needed in order to share the Gospel with Muslims.

Missionary Strategy

Results show that 34 (50%) of the respondents' felt it was often used, 23 (33.8%) felt that it was sometimes used, with 10 (14.7%) thinking that it was very often used. This reveals a reasonable level of use of missionary strategy, but suggests that it is not done efficiently, since not all members accepted that it is used. Hence the church should encourage its use in order to share the gospel with Muslims.

Development of Adventist Learning Institutions

Results show that 27 (39.7%) of the respondents felt that having an Adventist learning education institution was a good strategy, though a reasonable number 24 (35.4=3%) felt that it is sometimes used and 8 (11.8%) said that it is never used. This reveals how inefficiently and ineffectively the strategy is used and calls for more efforts in using this strategy to share the gospel with Muslims in Malakal. This could be done through the construction and operation of more SDA schools, colleges, and even a university, which would accommodate both SDA Christians and Muslims.

Use of Extreme Media (TV, Radio, Newspapers)

Findings show that 36 (52.9%) of the respondents accepted that sometimes-extreme media such as TV, radio, and newspapers are used by Adventist Church to share the gospel with Muslims. This indicates that the strategy is not satisfactorily used, as some respondents felt, and hence the church should efficiently and effectively use the strategy through introducing its own local TV, radio, or printed matter to share the gospel with other people, including the Muslim community, since many of the international media may be difficult to understand.

Use of Social Media

The findings reveal that 31 (45.6%) feel that social media is sometimes used, while 4 (5.9%) responded that it was used very often, and 18 (26.5%) reported that it was often used to share the gospel with other people, including the Muslims. From the results, it is clear that not all people use social media, yet it seems like an effective strategy. Therefore, more efforts should be placed in the use of social media platforms such as Facebook, Messenger, and WhatsApp by SDA members to share the gospel with Muslims.

Use of the Testimonies

Results reveal that this strategy is sometimes used, as 34 (50%) of the respondents reported. There is a great need for more efforts to use the testimony strategy (telling what Jesus has done for you in your life) to convince and encourage Muslims to come to the SDA church.

Reasons that Lead to Reluctance of Adventists to Vigorously Share the Gospel with Muslims

The second objective of the study was to identify the key reasons that led to reluctance of Adventist members to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends. The results are presented in frequency and percentage counts in Table 3 of the study.

The empirical results in Table 3 present information on how factors such as Islamic Sharia, intimidating world view, beliefs, and disunity among the gospel workers and economic factors lead to reluctance of Adventists to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslims in Malakal.

Table 3: Reasons that lead to reluctance of Adventists to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslims

Items	Yes	Not Sure	No
Islamic Sharia (Law) Factors			
Attitudes and prejudices of Muslims towards Christianity	28 (41.2%)	30 (44.1%)	10 (14.7%)
Islam seen as superior to every other religion in the area	45 (66.2%)	18 (26.5%)	5 (7.4%)
Lack of the knowledge of Islam for Adventists to convince Muslims	46 (67.6%)	18 (26.5%)	4 (5.9%)
Christian Perspective			
Slow growth of SDA discouraging the workers	19 (27.9%)	35 (51.5%)	14 (20.6%)
Christians' dismissal of Muhammad	28 (41.2%)	31 (45.6%)	9 (13.2%)
Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament			
Recognition of Quran by Christians	30 (44.1%)	29 (42.6%)	9 (13.2%)
Recognition of Bible and Jesus by Muslims	37 (54.4%)	27 (39.7%)	4 (5.9%)
Attitude of Muslims regarding Jesus as Son of God	41 (60.3%)	25 (36.8%)	2 (2.9%)
Muslims' Attitude towards the "TRINITY"	26 (38.2%)	34 (50%)	8 (11.8%)
Attitude of Muslims on Jesus' death, crucifixion, and resurrection	28 (41.2%)	34 (50%)	6 (8.8%)
Muslims' "FEAR OF PERSECUTION"	46 (67.6%)	18 (26.5%)	4 (5.9%)
Disunity			
Social connection between Christians and Muslims in Malakal	26 (38.2%)	38 (55.9%)	4 (5.9%)
Gospel Commission	30 (44.1%)	30 (44.1%)	8 (11.8%)
Islam's shortcoming to meet humankind's moral and spiritual needs	27 (39.7%)	33 (48.5%)	8 (11.8%)
Lack of resources to spread the Gospel	31(45.6%)	32 (47.1%)	5 (7.4%)
Poverty level among the residents	35 (51.5%)	26 (38.2%)	7 (10.3%)

Islamic Sharia (Law) Factors

Results show that 30 (44.1%) of the Adventist respondents were not sure whether attitudes and prejudices of Muslims towards Christianity were factors affecting the spread of the Gospel. On the other hand, 45 (66.2%) felt that Muslims take Islam as a superior to other religions.

Christian Perspective

Results reveal that 35 (51.5 %) of the respondents were not sure whether the slow growth of the Adventist Church was hindering their chance to share the Gospel with Muslims, just as their dismissal of Mohammed as the prophet of God made it hard for them to share the Gospel with Muslims. This shows that Christian factors were not clearly regarded as hindrance to Adventist members from sharing the Gospel with Muslims in Malakal.

Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament

The findings indicate that intimidation between Muslims and Christians about the validity of each religion affected or hindered Adventist members from sharing the Gospel with Muslims. For instance, 30 (44.1%) of the Adventist respondents accepted that they were not recognizing the Quran, but 37 (54.4%) felt that Muslims were not recognizing the Bible. Forty-one (60.3%) had the feeling that Muslims had a negative attitude towards Jesus being referred to as the Son of God, and about whether He resurrected or not. With this feeling, many Adventist members fail to share the Gospel with Muslims.

Disunity

Findings show that that SDA members may not share the Gospel with Muslims due to disunity, since 38 (55.9%) of the respondents were not sure of the

social connection between Adventists and Muslims. On the other hand, 33 (48.5%) were not sure whether Islam felt that Christianity met moral expectations and spiritual needs.

Economic Factors

The results reveal that economic factors, such as the lack of resources to spread the Adventist message and poverty among Adventist members, affected the ability to share the Gospel with Muslims. Of the respondents, 31 (45.6%) blamed lack of resources and 35 (51.5%) blamed poverty as hindrances for the Adventist members to share the gospel with Muslims.

CHAPTER 7

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter includes the summary, conclusions, and recommendations based on the data presented and analyzed in the preceding chapters. The summary and conclusions are drawn from the findings in regard to the study objectives.

Summary

This study was carried out on barriers to sharing the Gospel with Muslims in Malakal. There were three specific objectives: to investigate major strategies used by Adventist Church members to share the Gospel with the Muslim neighbors or friends, to identify the key reasons that lead to reluctance of Adventist members to not vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends. This chapter will identify recommended motivational strategies that might enable the Adventist church to more effectively share the Gospel with Muslim friends in Malakal.

Strategies such as house-to-house evangelism, person-to-person evangelism, and public evangelism in villages and in urban areas have not commonly been used in the Malakal area. It was also noted that there was no Adventist learning institution in the area and the use of extreme media (TV, radio, newspapers) and social media was poor. Respondents reported that Adventist members who share the Gospel with Muslim neighbors or friends sometimes used their testimonies.

Reasons such as Islamic Sharia Law factors, intimidating worldview, beliefs, disunity, and economy-related factors led to reluctance of Adventist members to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends

Motivational Factors and Strategies

This section summarizes the motivational factors mentioned in chapter 4, and also briefly discusses four motivational strategies. A motivational factor is an element that creates a context for motivation; motivational strategies are approaches or plans that focus an issue or opportunity towards accomplishing a goal in the heart and mind of the Adventist Church member.

Motivational Factors

The following are the motivational factors drawn from the research:

1. Most of the challenges discussed in this paper, if carefully handled, could be possibly used as bridges to share the Gospel with Muslims, instead of being blocks for gospel outreach to Muslims.
2. The fact that some countries, for example, South Sudan, do not have legal restrictions for Muslim conversion to Christianity; and Muslims and Christians are socially connected, could possibly motivate the Christian to share the Gospel with Muslims.
3. Muslims are included in Jesus' great commission, and have the right to hear the Gospel.
4. Islam is a missionary religion. If Christians fail to win Muslims to Christ, Muslims will win Christians to Islam.
5. Seventh-day Adventists should continue to work and pray for Muslims' conversion because of the Muslims' value in the sight of God.
6. Christians can and should reflect God's compassion for the hurting and the lost. Especially, in relation to the current socio-religious, economic, and political developments in the Middle East, many people are in need of help and love.

7. In Islam there is no redeemer or redemption, and no guarantee of forgiveness and peace with God. Only Christianity can bring this peace.

Motivational Strategies

1. Regular Training Sessions

One of the major motivational strategies for local church members and those who are involved in Muslim Ministries is a regular basic training in the area of witnessing to Muslims. In *Keys to Motivating Members to Witness*, Edited by May-Ellen Colon, on-the-job training is suggested to dissolve the fear of failure:

A trainer-trainee plan with on-the-job training can be one of the best methods of motivation. Jesus, the greatest motivator, took members with Him and showed them how to work. Fear of failure evaporates with this method. Members find that the activity is not difficult. It is much easier than anticipated. It is equally important to train a soul winner as to win a soul. Every member needs the spiritual experience obtained from sharing Jesus and His message and the challenge of reaching the world. Advise and motivate those giving Bible studies alone to become trainers and to, if possible, never give a Bible study alone. Always take a trainee. Both will be blessed.¹

2. Sharing Personal Testimonies

Sharing the stories of success by the participants in Muslim's Ministries can also do much in motivation. In life there is the rule that

Nothing succeeds like success. When members hear of the success of other members like themselves, they want to experience the same joy and want to have a part. As the member shares, it helps to eliminate two prevalent fears that enslave most fellow members: 'No one will listen to me,' and 'I wouldn't know what to say.' A witnessing story told by an in-experienced new or older member is much more effective in motivating others than one told by a paid pastor.²

¹May-Ellen Colon, ed., *Keys to Motivating Members to Witness* (Lincoln, NE: Advent Source, 2010), 21, 22, www.adventsource.org

²Ibid., 15.

3. Helping the Members Involved in Witnessing to Muslims to Engage in Planning, Setting Goals, and Assessments.

Engaging the witnessing team in planning also is another element for motivation.

Planning is crucial in any setting. As the famous saying goes, “failure to plan is planning to fail.” Colon explains:

People take better care of their own babies than the babies of others. When they own the plan, having formulated it, and set specific goals and target dates, they are much more likely to carry out their plan and reach their goals than if told what to do. And the good news is that when the members make their own plans and set their own goals, they are motivated to set them much higher than envisioned by the leaders, or when they are told what to do.³

4. Prayer Ministry

A final crucial motivational method is a prayer ministry. Prayer may help the church members to see Muslims as God sees them—as sinners who need a Savior. Prayer, whether privately or in groups, will greatly encourage those who are involved in witnessing to Muslims. God is the best motivator. In recognition of that, Jesus urged His disciples to pray for the labor and the laborers (John 10:2). Ellen G. White confirms that we should “ask God daily to motivate certain individuals. Then urge them to claim from Jesus His love for souls, as stated above, to give themselves to God for the saving of the lost, and to claim the daily baptism of the Holy Spirit. He will motivate.”⁴

Conclusions

Christians in Malakal need more than strategies if they are to witness to their Muslim neighbors and friends. They might be motivated to minister to Muslims when

³Ibid., 18.

⁴Ibid., 14.

they catch a glimpse of the existential worry and the all-encompassing darkness which Islam truly brings to a Muslim soul.

Adventist members may be motivated to share their faith regardless of the result when they look around and see Muslims empty, hurting, lost, confused, helpless, ashamed, struggling to find peace with God. They need to recognize that their Muslim friends are afraid of the judgment, afraid of speaking their mind, afraid of losing their status in the community, ashamed at what Islam has become. When they see these things, someone might sit up and say, I need to do something.

We need to understand that this is more than a theological or doctrinal battle. It is a matter of life or death; of giving light in darkness, hope for the hopeless, and help for the helpless.

We can explain the current socio-religious and economic and political developments in the Middle East and other regions of the Muslim World. We can identify major techniques and methods of evangelism. But what we really need is to realize the very personal existential implications and realities of individual Muslims (and the Muslim world). They face confusion, uncertainty, insecurity, threat, shame, fear, loss of control, powerlessness, hopelessness, resentment, anger, and/or an identity crisis. They experience these things in relation to the contemporary issues that confront them.

In the end, we are not to engage Islam! Rather, we engage Muslims. People. Human beings. We need empathy and compassion as we try to reflect God's compassion for the hurting and the lost. Haroon Moghul supported the idea with these words: "The Muslim world appears broken—unable to take care of its own, unable to solve its conflicts, unable, it seems, to be moved to care. . . . Many Muslims feel

helpless, disgusted, ashamed.”⁵ As servants of a loving God, we need to reach out to these neighbors whose hearts are hurting with the good news of the Gospel.

We need to assist members to understand the difference between Islam and an individual Muslim. This deeper understanding of the Muslim as a person yields opportunities for service and sharing. A deeper knowledge of the existential, moral, and spiritual impact of Islam as a worldview on the Muslim person is crucial. This understanding can awaken a deeper sense in us of their lostness and their need of hope and true peace and an understanding of who God really is and the wonderful redemption that is afforded through Jesus Christ.

Recommendations

Recommended Approaches

1. Adventist members need to learn and implement strategies to communicate the Gospel more effectively to Muslims in Malakal. The Adventist Church needs to put more effort into public and personal evangelism in order to share the Gospel with Muslims in Malakal. This will require time and finances.
2. House-to-house visitation is not much used, but if effectively used, might help the church to communicate the Gospel to the Muslims.
3. More efforts are needed to share the Gospel with Muslims in Malakal through Adventist primary and secondary schools. A university, open to Christians and Muslims could be a good evangelistic method.
4. The Church should efficiently and effectively use communication strategies, through introducing its own local TV, radio, or magazine/newspaper to share

⁵Haroon Moghul, "The Muslim World Is Broken: It Doesn't Have To Be," CNN September 3, 2015, <https://edition.cnn.com/2015/09/03/opinions/moghul-refugee-response-muslim-countries/index.html>.

the Gospel with other people, including the Muslim community. Since many of the media available for Adventist evangelism are international, which are sometimes hard to understand, programs and reading material need to be in the local language.

5. More efforts should be placed on the use of social media platforms such as Facebook, Messenger, and WhatsApp by Adventist members, to share the Gospel with Muslims. This is especially true with the younger generation.

Recommended Understandings

1. Assist members to understand the difference between Islam and an individual Muslim.
2. Help them see that their neighbors are lost and need hope and true peace, an understanding of who God really is, and to hear the news of the wonderful redemption through Jesus Christ.
3. Help members reach out to their Muslim neighbor's souls in terms of understanding the fear that every Muslim experiences. Help them see how they might touch a Muslim's hurting heart—by relating to them as human beings.
4. Engage Adventist Church members in helping them identify their own prejudices, preferences, presuppositions, etc., which hinder them from being motivated to minister to Muslims. Adventists create their own barriers in addition to that which Islam creates.
5. Regular training of the Adventist church members at the level of the local Church about basic information about Islam and Muslims is highly needed and could possibly motivate them to share the Gospel with Muslims wherever possible. The training should help make a clear distinction between Islam and

a Muslim and develop a sensitivity to the existential realities of individual Muslims with respect to the confusion, uncertainty, and anger, which they experience in relation to the contemporary issues that confront them.

6. Somehow members need to be led to reflect on the existential implications for the contemporary Muslim so as to experience deeper compassion and commitment in self-sacrificial service to individual Muslims in bringing them hope, peace, and assurance in Christ (Matt 9:36; Col 3:12).

Recommendations for Further Research

In this study I have focused on the challenges, which have led to the reluctance of the Seventh-day Adventist Church members in Malakal. I have also noted the opportunities, which could have motivated them to share the Gospel with the Muslims. However, during the study some issues were encountered that require further research. Among these are the Islamic Law of Apostates, Muslims' fear of persecution, and Christians' lack of knowledge concerning Islam. These are among the top challenges, which lead to the reluctance of Christians to witness among Muslims. More research could be helpful in these areas, since they were only briefly discussed in this research. Furthermore, I have realized the reality of the reluctance among the Seventh-day Adventist members and the need to motivate them spiritually, as well as with training. These discoveries are good areas for further study.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- al-Fadi, Abd. "The Sonship of Christ in The Qur'an" *The Person of Christ in the Gospel and the Quran* (2010), 23-30. https://info1.sermon-online.com/english/TheGoodWay/The_Person_Of_Christ_In_The_Gospel_And_The_Koran_1975.doc
- Abd-al-Ati, Hammudah. *Islam in Focus*. 3rd ed. Beltsville, MD: Amana Publications, 1998.
- Abdul-Haqq, Abdiyah Akbar. *Sharing Your Faith with a Muslim*, Minneapolis, MN: Bethany House, 1980.
- Azumah, John. *My Neighbour's Faith: Islam Explained for Christians*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2008.
- Bauer, Bruce L., ed. *Faith Development in Context*. Berrien Springs, MI: Department of World Mission, Andrews University, 2010.
- _____. "Avoid Comfortable Syncretism by Doing Critical Contextualization." *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 1 (2005): 18-32.
- Bethmann, Erich W. *Bridge to Islam: A Study of the Religious Forces of Islam and Christianity in the Near East*. London, UK: G. Allen and Unwin, 1963.
- Chase, Jerry. "A Voice from the Back Seat." *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 1 (2005): 86-94.
- Colon, May-Ellen, ed., *Keys to Motivating Members to Witness*. Lincoln, NE: Advent Source, 2010. www.adventsource.org.
- Deng, Jack A. Abubakar. "Vers Enteries: Islam in South Sudan" [مقالات: الإسلام في [جنوب السودان], www.sudaress.com/sudansite/649.
- Dizon, Abner P. "Issues in Adventist Muslim Ministry." *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 8 (2012): 5-17.
- Doss, Cheryl, ed. *Passport to Mission*. 3rd ed. Berrien Springs, MI: Andrews University Press, 2009.
- Dybdahl, Jon L., ed. *Adventist Mission in the 21st Century: The Joy and Challenges of Presenting Jesus to a Diverse World*. Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald, 1999.
- Edwards, Rex D. *Every Believer a Minister*. Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald, 1995.

- Fadlalla, Mohamad Hassan. *Short History of Sudan*. New York: iUniverse, 2004.
- Fitzgerald, Troy. "Good Going." *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 3 (2007): 30-35.
- Gilchrist, John. *Answering Islam*. <https://answering-islam.org/authors/gilchrist.html>.
- _____. *Sharing the Gospel with Muslims: A Handbook for Bible-based Muslim Evangelism*. Nairobi, Kenya: Oasis International, 2003.
- _____. *Facing the Muslim Challenge: A Handbook of Christian-Muslim Apologetics*. Cape Town, South Africa: Life Challenge Africa, 2004.
- Karst, Gerald D. "Light Breaks Over Sudan." *Mission: A Quarterly Report of World Mission*, April-June 1987: 20-22.
- Knowles, George E. *How to Help Your Church Grow*. Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald, 1997.
- Lewis, Bernard. *What Went Wrong? The Clash between Islam and Modernity in the Middle East*. New York, NY: HarperCollins, 2000.
- Livingstone, Greg. *Planting Churches in Muslim Cities: A Team Approach*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker, 1993.
- Love, Rick. *Muslims, Magic and the Kingdom of God*. Pasadena, CA: William Carey Library, 2000.
- McEdwards, Rick. "A Brief Overview of Adventist Witness among Muslims." In *A Man of Passionate Reflection: A Festschrift Honoring Jerald Whitehouse*, ed. Bruce L. Bauer, 237-252. Berrien Springs, MI: Department of World Mission, Andrews University.
- Miller, William McElwee. *A Christian's Response to Islam*. Phillipsburg, NJ: Presbyterian and Reformed, 1979.
- Moghul, Haroon. "The Muslim World Is Broken: It Doesn't Have To Be." *CNN* September 3, 2015. <https://edition.cnn.com/2015/09/03/opinions/moghul-refugee-response-muslim-countries/index.html>
- Nehls, Gerhard, and Walter Eric. *Christian-Islamic Controversy*. Nairobi, Kenya: Life Challenge Africa, 2006.
- _____. *Islam: Basic Aspects*. Nairobi, Kenya: Life Challenge Africa, 2005.
- _____. *A Practical-Tactical Approach to Muslim Evangelism*. Nairobi, Kenya: Life Challenge Africa, 1997.
- _____. *Reach Out: What Every Christian Needs to Know about Islam and Muslims*. Nairobi, Kenya: Life Challenge Africa, 2009.

- Osindo, Oscar. "Relating to Mohammad and the Mosque," in *Faith Development in Context: Presenting Christ in Creative Ways*, ed. Bruce Bauer. Berrien Springs, MI: Andrews University Press, 2005.
- Parshall, Philip. *Muslim Evangelism: Contemporary Approaches to Contextualization*. Waynesboro, GA: Gabriel, 2003.
- Shenunda III, Pope. "Trinity and Unity." Lecture delivered at the Cathedral of St. Mark in Cairo 2010, 2, <http://www.the-good-way.com>.
- Roth, Ray. "Attitude and Approaches to the Evangelization of the Muslims in the Middle East," Doctor of Ministry dissertation, Andrews University 183. <https://digitalcommons.andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1206&content=dmin>.
- Saal, William J. *Reaching Muslims for Christ*. Chicago, IL: Moody Press, 1993.
- Schantz, Borge. *Islam in the Post 9/11 World*. Grantham, Lincs, England: Autumn House, 2003.
- _____. *Your Muslim Friends and You*. Bracknell, Berkshire, England: Seventh-day Adventist Global Center for Islamic Studies, 1993.
- Schantz, Borge, and Stephen Thompson, *Biblical Missionaries* (Nampa, ID: Pacific Press, 2015).
- Swartley, Keith, ed. *Encountering the World of Islam*. Waynesboro, GA: Authentic Media, 2005
- Sweazey, George E. *Effective Evangelism: The Greatest Work in the World*. New York: Harper & Row, 1953.
- Terry, John Mark. In Keith E. Swartley, ed. *Encountering the World of Islam*, (pp. 314-319). Waynesboro, GA: Authentic Media, 2005.
- Towns, Elmer L. *Winning the Winnable*. Elmer L. Towns, 1987.
- Vyhmeister, Nancy Jean. *Your Guide to Writing Quality Research Papers for Students of Religion and Theology*, 2nd ed. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2008.
- Wani, Abdalla Keri. *Islam in Southern Sudan: Its Impacts, Past, Present, and Future*. Khartoum, Sudan: Khartoum University Publishing, 2006.
- Wagner, William. *How Islam Plans to Change the World*. Grand Rapids: Kregel, 2004.
- White, Ellen G. "Committed to Reaching Everyone." *Adventist World*, November 2010, 22, 23.
- Whitehouse, Jerald. "God's Footprints in the Rubble: Adventist Muslim Relations during Crisis." *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies* 1 (2005): 5-13.

APPENDIX

SELF-ADMINISTERED QUESTIONNAIRE

(Adventist Church Members)

Dear Respondents,

My name is **GAK NGAW NYOAT DOAK** and I am carrying out a study on **“BARRIERS TO SHARING THE GOSPEL WITH MUSLIM FRIENDS IN MALAKAL.”** It is my sincere request that you provide me with information relevant to this study. The study will enable me complete the requirement of a master’s degree Master of Arts in Islamic Studies of **MIDDLE EAST UNIVERSITY**. All information provided will be for academic purposes and will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Thank you for accepting and sparing you time to fill in this questionnaire. Please do not write any information that identifies you, such as name, ID, or others.

Thank you for your cooperation and time.

Section A: Background Information

Instructions: Please tick where applicable.

1: Gender: a. Male [] b. Female []

2: Church Membership Period A. Less than 1 year [], B. 1-5 years [], C. 6-10 years [], D. 11-15 years [] E. 16 years and above [].

Section B: Objective Questions

Strategies Used by Adventist Church Members to Share the Gospel with the Muslim Neighbors

Please state your response on the level in which the following strategies are used by Adventist Church members to share the Gospel with the Muslim neighbors or friends based on the four-point Likert scale of;

4. Very Often (VO), 3. Often (O), 2. Sometimes (S), 1. Never (N)

Strategies used to share the Gospel with Muslims	Response			
	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Never
1. House to house evangelism				
2. Person to person evangelism				
3. Use of open crusades in villages				
4. Use of open crusades in urban areas				
5. Missionary strategy				
6. Use of SDA learning institutions				
7. Use of extreme media (TV, radio, newspapers)				
8. Use of social media				
9. Use of the testimonies				

Reasons that Lead to Reluctance of Adventist Members to Vigorously Share the Gospel with Muslim Friends

Please state how the following factors makes the Adventist Church members reluctant to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends based on a 3 point Likert Scale of: 3. Yes (Y), 2. Not Sure (NS), 1. No (N).

Factors that make the Adventist Church members reluctant to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim

Response

Islamic Sharia (Law) Factors

Yes Not Sure No

1. Attitudes and prejudices of Muslims
2. Islam superior to every other religion
3. Islam seen as superior to every other religion

Christian Perspective

Yes Not Sure No

4. Lack of the knowledge of Islam
5. Slow growth of SDA discouraging the workers

Intimidating Worldview, Beliefs, and Temperament

Yes Not Sure No

6. Christians Dismissal of Muhammad
7. Recognition of Quran by Christians
8. Recognition of Bible and Jesus by Muslims
9. Attitude of Muslims on Jesus as Son of God
10. Muslims' Attitude towards "TRINITY"
11. Attitude of Muslims on Jesus Death, Crucifixion, and Resurrection
12. Muslims "FEAR OF PERSECUTION"

Disunity among the Gospel Workers

Yes Not Sure No

13. Social connection between Christian and Muslims in Malakal
14. Gospel Commission
15. Islam's Shortcoming to meet human kind's moral and Spiritual needs

Economic Factors

16. Lack of resources to spread the gospel
17. Poverty level among the residents

Section C: Suggestions

What do you think are the suitable motivational strategies to be applied to enable the Adventist Church to vigorously share the Gospel with Muslim friends in Malakal?

CURRICULUM VITAE

Personal Information

Name: Gak Ngaw Nyoat Doak
Date of Birth: January 1, 1972.
Place of Birth: Nasir, South Sudan
Sex: Male
Marital status: Married to Nyanhail Peter Pal Riek, July 27, 1991
Nationality: South Sudanese
Languages: Nuer, Arabic, and English.
Contacts: Mobile +21192138993/ +211916400837/+25678827009
Email: gakgunf72@gmail.com

Children

Musa, April 12, 1992, Khartoum, Sudan, Khan, November 25, 1998,
Renk, South Sudan,
Naphtali, June 27, 2004, Khartoum, Sudan,
Nyagony, May 30, 2006, Khartoum, Sudan,
Pal, September 17, 2012, Malakal, South Sudan

Educational Background

2011-2020 Master of Arts, in Islamic Studies and Arabic, Middle East
University, Beirut, Lebanon
2004-2010 Bachelor of Arts, in Pastoral Ministry, Middle East University
off-campus programme, Arua, Uganda
1993-1996 Sudan Secondary School Certificate, Shendi Boys, High School,
Shendi, Sudan
1989-1992 Certificate of intermediate Education, Al- Kalakala Al -Ghala
Intermediate School, Khartoum, Sudan
1981-1987 Certificate of Primary Education, Bhender Boys Primary School,
Malakal, South Sudan

Work Experience

Jan 2012-present Executive Secretary Greater Upper Nile Field of the Seventh-
day Adventist Church Malakal, South Sudan.
2009-Dec 2011 Youth Director, Sudan Field of Adventist Church
Jan 2006 Dec 2011 District Pastor, Sudan Field of Adventist Church, Renk, Sudan.
Oct 21, 2006 Ordination to the Gospel Ministry, Khartoum, Sudan
Jan 2003 – Dec 2005 Primary School Teacher, FEEDA Primary School, Soba Aradi,
Khartoum
Sep 1998 – Dec 2005 Gospel Worker, Sudan Field of Adventist Church, Renk,
/Hatana, Umdureman, and Soba Aradi, Khartoum, Sudan.